

Evaluation of an ice rink energy management concept comprising CO₂ refrigeration

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Master degree programme *Sustainable Energy Competence*

Master of Science Thesis
Division of Applied Thermodynamics and Refrigeration

Acknowledgements

I would say act like a man of thought and think like a man of action.

(Henri Bergson)

First of all, I'd like to thank Jürgen Rogstam for his feedback, support and patience throughout my thesis.

Furthermore, I like to thank Prof. Dr. Sawalha and Ph.D. cand. Mazyar Karampour for their time, competent support and notes to my work.

Many thanks to my parents, who supported me throughout my past 27 years in a great way. Moreover, I'd like to thank my brothers and my friends for their companionship.

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Declaration

I, Frederik Banis, hereby declare that this master thesis has been written only by the undersigned and without any assistance from third parties. Furthermore I confirm that no sources have been used in the preparation of this thesis other than those indicated in the work itself.

Stockholm, February 4

Abstract

Ice rinks in conjunction with a refrigeration system using CO₂ in trans-critical conditions are a system set-up increasingly often used due to a good overall system performance. Main reasons are that both heat and cold are the major demands in ice rinks and CO₂ is competitive for such application. Furthermore, CO₂ can be used as single refrigerant since this refrigerant is non-toxic. The *Gimo* ice rink near Stockholm in Sweden is such facility and equipped with a monitoring system recording major system parameters and hence enabling a more in-depth analysis of the system performance and system behaviour. Moreover, a geothermal storage is part of this ice rink. Thus, *Gimo* is interesting and well suited for the evaluation of energy management.

In this thesis, methods have been developed to calculate and analyse the cooling capacity, heat loads, and respective energy system performance. Indoor- and outdoor air conditions and the interaction of several system parameters and these conditions have been analysed. Furthermore, the system performance for different heat- and cold loads, as well as the optimization potential of the system performance have been evaluated.

Moreover, the subsystems of the facility — the heat recovery-, electricity-, and the geothermal storage system — have been analysed. A calculation of the heat potential of the heat recovery system has been carried out for two simplified scenarios. Furthermore, the performance of several system components has been evaluated.

In order to show the potential increase of the system performance using an internal heat exchanger, calculations have been carried out based on measured data and parameter variations. The main parameter altered was the efficiency of the heat exchanger. As part of this calculation, the impact of this internal heat exchanger on the heat recovery potential was also examined. The calculation suggested that the overall system performance can be increased using an internal heat exchanger at the chosen position, connecting the end of the gas cooler and the suction line of the compressors.

Two different ice temperature control strategies have been compared and evaluated. It was shown that the control of the ice temperature benefits from a control using an infra-red sensor that measures the ice surface temperature in favour of measuring the inner ice temperature with an embedded temperature sensor.

The CO₂ mass flow in the rink floor tubes has been estimated by filtering data for super-heat conditions at the rink floor tubes return.

Key words: CO₂, carbon dioxide, refrigeration system, trans-critical, ice rink, data analysis with python

Table of contents

Abstract	V
List of Figures	IX
List of Tables	XIII
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Objectives	2
1.3 Methodology	3
1.4 CO ₂ as a refrigerant	3
1.5 Ice rinks	4
1.5.1 Ice rinks in general	4
1.5.2 <i>Gimo</i> ice rink	5
2 Data processing	15
2.1 Data acquisition	15
2.1.1 Working with generated timestamps and derived data	15
2.1.2 Analysed measurement periods	18
2.1.3 Fluid property	19
2.2 Data visualization	19
2.2.1 Kernel density estimates	20
2.2.2 Violinplots	20
2.2.3 Correlations using quantiles	22
3 Calculation of operating parameters and specific system studies	24
3.1 CO ₂ circuit	24
3.1.1 CO ₂ mass flow in the main circuit	24
3.1.2 Efficiency of the compressors	25
3.1.3 Rejected and recovered heat in the gas cooler	25
3.1.4 Cooling capacity	28
3.1.5 Coefficients of performance	28
3.1.6 Heat recovery ratio	30
3.1.7 Optimal discharge pressure for maximizing the COP	30
3.1.8 Efficiency of the dry cooler	30
3.1.9 System performance with an internal heat exchanger	31
3.1.10 Ice temperature control	34
3.1.11 Rink floor CO ₂ mass flow and –pressure drop	40
3.2 Hot water circuit	43
3.2.1 Efficiency of the heat exchanger 1 (HX1)	44
3.2.2 Hot water circuit heat potential	44
3.3 Geothermal storage circuit	46

3.3.1	Efficiency of the heat exchanger 2	46
3.3.2	Deduced mixture mass flow	46
3.3.3	Geothermal storage ground temperature	47
3.4	Electricity systems	48
3.5	Air properties and dehumidification system	48
3.5.1	Calculation of air properties	48
3.5.2	Dehumidification system	49
4	General system analysis	50
4.1	Basic energy data	50
4.2	Basic power data of the cooling unit	55
4.3	Indoor– and ambient air conditions	62
4.4	General system performance	66
4.5	System behaviour	68
4.5.1	Influence of ambient conditions	68
4.5.2	Influence of indoor conditions	75
4.5.3	Load dependencies	75
4.6	Components	82
4.6.1	Dry cooler performance	82
4.6.2	Compressors	82
4.6.3	Dehumidification system	84
4.7	Subsystems	88
4.7.1	Hot water circuit	88
4.7.2	Geothermal storage	98
4.7.3	Electricity systems	102
5	Specific system analysis	109
5.1	Heat demand for additional heated space	109
5.2	Monitoring system COP calculation	109
5.3	System performance with an internal heat exchanger	109
5.4	Rink floor	113
5.4.1	Ice temperature control	113
5.4.2	CO ₂ rink mass flow and –pressure drop	117
6	Conclusions and suggestions for future works	120
	Bibliography	122

List of Figures

1.1	Comparison of fluid properties of Carbon Dioxide and Ammonia	4
1.2	Energy distribution in Swedish ice rinks.	5
1.3	Location of <i>Gimo</i> in Sweden.	6
1.4	Idealized transcritical refrigeration process	7
1.5	Temperature levels in the gas cooler	8
1.6	Simplified scheme of the cooling unit.	9
1.7	Simplified scheme of the hot water circuit.	11
1.8	Simplified scheme of the geothermal storage.	13
1.9	Simplified scheme of the dehumidifier.	14
2.1	Acquired data and generated timestamps with derived data.	17
2.2	Correlation coefficients for different re-sampling resolutions	18
2.3	Measurement periods and defined main samples.	19
2.4	Overview over the available amount of data per period.	20
2.5	Example of one dimensional kernel density estimates	21
2.6	Example of two dimensional kernel density estimates	21
2.7	Example of a boxplot and a violinplot	22
2.8	Example for correlations using quantiles over defined sectors	23
3.1	Energy balance over the compressors	25
3.2	Real- and ideal specific isentropic compression work	26
3.3	Rejected- and recovered heat in the gas cooler	28
3.4	Gas cooling section in the refrigeration unit	29
3.5	Cooling unit with an internal heat exchanger	31
3.6	Reference cycle and cycle with an internal heat exchanger compared	32
3.7	Correlation of compressor power demand and CO ₂ mass flow.	33
3.8	Ice temperature sensor signal comparison	34
3.9	Algorithm for the evaluation of re-surfacing control strategies	37
3.10	Detail of a day with traced re-surfacings by the algorithm, <i>Period 1</i>	38
3.11	Detail of a day with traced re-surfacings by the algorithm, <i>Period 2</i>	39
3.12	Response of ice temperature sensors and measured heat demand of the re-surfacer	39
3.13	Correlation between the rink pump signal and the compressor power demand	40
3.14	Correlation between rink pump signal and compressor power demand	41
3.15	Main- and rink floor CO ₂ circuit in the pressure-enthalpy diagram	42
3.16	Heat flows in the hot water circuit	43
3.17	Water mass flow distribution in the hot water circuit	44
3.18	Deduced water-glycol mass flow	47
3.19	Energy meter <i>E02</i> , power consumer behaviour	48
3.20	Simplified scheme of the dehumidifier.	49
4.1	Electric energies in the facility.	52
4.2	Energies in the CO ₂ cycle	53
4.3	Energies in the hot water circuit.	54

4.4	Weekly main heat and cold quantities in <i>Period 1</i>	57
4.5	Weekly main heat and cold quantities in <i>Period 2</i>	58
4.6	Weekly heat quantities in the gas cooler in <i>Period 1</i>	59
4.7	Weekly heat quantities in the gas cooler in <i>Period 2</i>	60
4.8	Hourly variation in load in the gas cooler in <i>Period 1</i>	61
4.9	Distribution of ambient– and indoor temperatures	62
4.10	Distribution of absolute ambient– and indoor humidities	63
4.11	Distribution of relative ambient– and indoor humidities	63
4.12	Correlation: Indoor- and outdoor temperature and humidity	65
4.13	Distribution of coefficients of performance	66
4.14	Weekly global COP data distribution	67
4.15	Correlation: Compressor power consumption and the ambient temp.	69
4.16	Correlation: Heat– and cold in the unit and the ambient temperature.	69
4.17	Correlation: Heat quantities in the gas cooler and the ambient temperature.	70
4.18	Correlation: Heat recovery ratio and the ambient temperature.	71
4.19	Correlation: Gas cooler exit temperature and the ambient temperature	71
4.20	Correlation: COP ₁ and COP ₀ and the ambient temperature.	72
4.21	Correlation: COP _{global} and the ambient temperature.	73
4.22	Correlation: Real– and optimal discharge pressure and the ambient temp.	74
4.23	Correlation: Cooling capacity, heat demand and the indoor air temperature	75
4.24	Data distribution of the gas cooler exit temperature	76
4.25	Correlation: COP ₁ and COP ₀ and the gas cooler exit temperature.	76
4.26	Correlation: COP _{global} and the the gas cooler exit temperature.	77
4.27	Correlation: Discharge pressure and heat recovery ratio	78
4.28	Correlation: COP _{global} and the heat recovery ratio.	79
4.29	Correlation: Real– and optimized discharge pressure and the HRR	80
4.30	Weekly data distribution of the discharge pressure	81
4.31	Distribution of calculated dry cooler efficiency	82
4.32	Distribution of calculated total compressor efficiency	83
4.33	Correlation: Total compressor efficiency and the pressure ratio	83
4.34	Weekly median values of the dehumidifier power sources	84
4.35	Temperature levels of the dehumidifier recovery air	85
4.36	Correlation: Dehumidifier efficiency and ambient temperature	85
4.37	Correlation: Power demand of the dehumidifier and difference of absolute air humidity	86
4.38	Distribution of heat quantities in the hot water circuit	89
4.39	Distribution of heat quantities in the hot water circuit for different hours of the day	91
4.40	Temperature trends in the hot water circuit	92
4.41	Correlation: Rejected heat to the hot water circuit and ambient temperature	93
4.42	Correlation: Heat demand of the radiators and the ambient temperature	93
4.43	Correlation: Heat demand for air heating and ambient temperature	94
4.44	Distribution of calculated <i>HXI</i> efficiencies	94
4.45	Correlation: <i>HXI</i> efficiency and the ratio of heat capacity rates.	95
4.46	Hot water circuit heat potential scenario 1 (<i>Period 1</i>)	96
4.47	Hot water circuit heat potential scenario 1 (<i>Period 2</i>)	96
4.48	Hot water circuit heat potential scenario 2 (<i>Period 1</i>)	97
4.49	Hot water circuit heat potential scenario 2 (<i>Period 2</i>)	97
4.50	Minimal geothermal return temperature evolution	98
4.51	Geothermal storage temperature and pump, trend of a day	99
4.52	Geothermal storage temperature and pump, detailed trend	99
4.53	Correlation: Absorbed heat in the geothermal storage and –pump signal	100

4.54	Correlation: Absorbed heat in the geothermal storage and efficiency of <i>HX2</i> . . .	101
4.55	Efficiency of the heat exchanger 2	101
4.56	Correlation: Efficiency of <i>HX2</i> and the ratio of heat capacity rates.	102
4.57	Compressor power and auxiliary power consumers in the facility.	103
4.58	Comparison of measured energy demand; facility and community	104
4.59	Derived overall electricity demand share	104
4.60	Distribution of compressor power demand	105
4.61	Distribution of electric power demand of rink pump, dry cooler fans and heating pumps	106
4.62	Overview over electric power demand of lighting and dehumidification.	107
4.63	Distribution of electric power demand for different hours of the day	108
5.1	Predicted heat demand for additional heated spaces.	109
5.2	Green & Cool COP compared to the scientifically correct value.	110
5.3	IHX study: System performance	111
5.4	IHX study: Available heat for the heat recovery system	112
5.5	IHX study: Heat demand and available heat	113
5.6	Fluctuation of cooling capacity and ice temperature compared	114
5.7	Comparison of ice temperature control concepts	115
5.8	Correlation: Deviation of the ice temperature from the set point and time needed to stabilize the ice temperature back on the latter	116
5.9	Comparison of the main- and the rink floor CO ₂ mass flow	117
5.10	Deduced CO ₂ rink floor mass flow as a function of the rink floor pump signal	117
5.11	Overview over receiver-, rink floor tubes inlet pressure and pressure drop	118
5.12	Correlation: Mass flow and pressure drop in the rink tubes	119

List of Tables

1.1	Heated rooms in the facility (main hall excluded)	12
1.2	Overview over used power meters	12
3.1	Comparison of measurement values of <i>PT2</i> and <i>PT3</i>	28
3.2	Light signal and corresponding values of the power meter <i>E02</i> compared.	48

1 Introduction

Contents

2.1	Data acquisition	15
2.1.1	Working with generated timestamps and derived data	15
2.1.2	Analysed measurement periods	18
2.1.3	Fluid property	19
2.2	Data visualization	19
2.2.1	Kernel density estimates	20
2.2.2	Violinplots	20
2.2.3	Correlations using quantiles	22

1.1 Background

Ice rinks have got a significant potential for saving energy. This is due that the average consumed amount of (primarily) electric energy per ice rink is high and the interaction of sub-systems is complex. Hence, a variety of optimizations can be applied to such system.

In the public sector, ice rinks are among the most energy intensive public buildings [10]; the average Swedish ice rink consumes approximately 1000 MWh/a [9]. Beside a high cooling demand, ice rinks are also demanding regarding the heating demand.

With an increase in restrictions regarding synthetic refrigerants, natural refrigerants are gain in importance once more. CO_2 is such a natural refrigerant, growing attractiveness not only due to safety reasons, "as it can be directly used in public areas" [17, p. 7]. Another positive aspect of CO_2 are its good properties regarding heat recovery in transcritical conditions. Furthermore, the temperature level in the gas cooler fits the need for heating purposes. For these reasons, CO_2 driven refrigeration systems working in transcritical conditions are able to provide sufficient amounts of heat at a sufficient temperature level.

While CO_2 has first been utilized as a secondary refrigerant due to its "good properties in term of pumping power"[8, p. 2], a growing number of ice rinks are built or renovated utilizing solely CO_2 in the refrigeration system, referred to as "direct expansion systems"[8, p. 4].

One of these CO_2 -only driven refrigeration systems is used in the Gimo ice rink in Sweden. This ice rink is one of the first in Europe working with CO_2 only. It features a geothermal storage as well as a monitoring system covering all major system parameters. Due to these conditions, the Gimo ice rink is interesting from a evaluation perspective.

1.2 Objectives

The objective of this thesis is the evaluation of the system performance. This evaluation is grouped in a general system analysis– and a specific system analysis part.

- General system analysis
 - System performance
 - * Cooling capacity
 - * Heat loads
 - * Coefficients of performance
 - * ...
 - Comparison of the system and sub-systems with the theoretical background
 - Sub-systems and their interaction
 - * Heat recovery system¹
 - * Geothermal storage circuit
 - Function
 - Control
 - Sizing
- Specific system analysis
 - Heat demand for additional heated spaces
 - Hot water circuit heat potential
 - System performance with an internal heat exchanger
 - Rink floor
 - * Ice temperature control strategies
 - * Rink floor concepts
 - System components
 - * Heat exchanger and dry cooler performance

¹Referred to later as *hot water circuit*.

- * Compressor performance
- * Rink floor CO₂ pump function
- * Lighting system
- * Dehumidification system

1.3 Methodology

In order to be able to evaluate the system, the acquired data is optimized and re-sampled first. Two measurement periods are considered, which differ in several aspects.

Methods are then developed for the calculation of operating parameters based on the re-sampled data, such as heat loads in the gas cooler and the cooling capacity, as well as for the analysis of several system components. Partly, regression models are used to deduce a function based on the data. This is the case for the mass flow in the geothermal storage circuit, the electric power share of the lighting system and the CO₂ pump. In the case of the geothermal storage pump, the derived pump function is then used for further calculations.

The data of the two periods are then evaluated and compared. The influence of ambient conditions and variations in load on the system are analysed using different data visualisation strategies.

Beside the analysis of measured- and derived data, the optimization potential is evaluated regarding the system performance with an internal heat exchanger and the heat potential in the hot water circuit. For these aspects, the system performance is modelled based on the measured data and variations of several parameters, as well as the usage of regression models.

1.4 CO₂ as a refrigerant

The usage of CO₂ for refrigeration purposes started at the end of the 19th century and it was used heavily in the early 20th century[11]. With the introduction of synthetic refrigerants, a shift to the latter took place, as they allowed for a better handling with the existing technology in those days. "The main reasons for the freewill phasing-out of CO₂ are its high operating pressure (about 64.2 bars at 25°C) and its low critical temperature of 31°C . This implied that CO₂ systems had containment problems"[17, p. 7].

Despite the handling of CO₂ remains sophisticated nowadays, it is a promising solution when several aspects are taken into account.

One quality of CO₂ in the trans-critical cycle is that it "allow[s] heat reclaim on a higher level than most other conventional systems"[8]. In many of the latter, heat is transferred to the ambient at the high pressure level solely by using a dry cooler. In CO₂ systems however, the available heat at the high pressure level can be utilized due to the properties of the fluid. Because of this advantage, the usage of CO₂ is competitive to conventional refrigerants, when heat of the working fluid is reclaimed and utilized to cover the heating demand.

Moreover, as environmental aspects gain weight, CO₂ is getting more attractive. It has got a low Global Warming Potential (GWP) of one, its Ozone Depletion Potential (ODP) relates to

zero [17, p. 8]. Furthermore it is "non-flammable, non-explosive, [...] relatively non-toxic [and] inexpensive"[17, p. 8].

As mentioned before, the working pressure of CO₂ is relatively high compared to other refrigerants. In comparison to Ammonia, the most commonly used refrigerant in ice rinks[13, p. 1], it is distinctively higher, cp. figure 1.1 (a).

CO₂ has a higher vapour density than Ammonia, being "an advantage to obtain a low volume flow for a given mass flow, [hence ensuring] small component size[s]"[6, p. 9]. While this is an advantage of CO₂, Ammonia has got a significantly higher specific latent heat in comparison. Yet, CO₂ shows a significantly higher volumetric refrigeration capacity in comparison. This is the reason for the already mentioned small component sizes, for example compressors.

As the pressure drop is inversely proportional to the volumetric refrigeration capacity, the pressure drop of CO₂ is much lower than Ammonia[17, p. 12].

Figure 1.1: Comparison of fluid properties of carbon dioxide and ammonia at saturation temperature. (a): Pressure as a function of the saturation temperature, (b): Saturated vapour density, (c): Latent heat as a function of the saturation temperature, (d): Volumetric refrigeration capacity.

(Source of data for carbon dioxide: [14], source of data for ammonia: [15][2])

1.5 Ice rinks

1.5.1 Ice rinks in general

As already mentioned, the energy demand of ice rinks is high, as they are among the most energy intensive public buildings. However, the spread depending on facility size is high. The consumed energy per year ranges "from 400 MWh to 4000 MWh or more for large arenas [per year]"[8].

Of this energy, a major part is used for refrigeration and heating purposes. Furthermore in this context, the size matters: "the relative share for the refrigeration system is typically higher in smaller ice rinks and reversed in larger" [8][9].

According to a report of the Swedish Energy Agency conducted in 2009, the consumed energy of the average Swedish ice rink is distributed as pointed out in figure 1.2.

The major share accounts to the refrigeration system with 43%, while the heating system at second position accounts for a share of 26%. The remaining 31% refer to lighting, fans, dehumidification of indoor air and miscellaneous consumers.

Figure 1.2: Energy distribution in Swedish ice rinks based on a study of the Swedish Energy Agency [9].

In an ice rink, several objectives influence each other. While a low power consume for cooling the ice is one aim, spectators in the hall need to have an adequate comfort, causing increased heat loads on the ice and therefore on the cooling system.

As pointed out by the American Society of Heating, Refrigeration and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE), the main heat load on to the ice sheet are [1]:

- Conductive loads
- Heat gains to the piping
- Heat gains from the coolant circulating pumps
- Ice re-surfacings
- Convections
- Radiation

1.5.2 *Gimo* ice rink

The *Gimo* ice rink is located in the southern-centre of Sweden, around 1.5 hours of drive per car north of its capital, Stockholm. Cp. figure 1.3 on the following page.

This ice rink features a CO₂ refrigeration system in trans-critical operation that supplies all the energy demands of cooling, heating, hot water supply and a share of the dehumidification demand. Furthermore, a geothermal storage circuit is part of the system, allowing for further sub-cooling of CO₂ in the gas cooler and storing energy. As the system can also work as a heat pump, stored

energy can be utilized when needed. The ice rink is equipped with sensors to measure major system parameters and consequently enabling for the analysis and optimization of the system performance and control strategy.

Figure 1.3: Location of *Gimo* in Sweden.

The only cooling demand in this ice rink is for cooling the ice sheet. However, there are several heat demands in the facility, as will be presented in the following sections.

The mentioned cooling– and heating demands are supplied by three circuits:

- CO₂ circuit
- Hot water circuit
- Geothermal storage circuit

The CO₂ circuit is the main circuit, while the hot water circuit and the geothermal storage circuit are referred to as sub–systems later on.

In the following, an overview over these main circuits in the facility is given.

CO₂ circuit

The simplified cyclic refrigeration process is composed of four processes:

- Compression
- Gas cooling
- Decompression
- Evaporation

The gaseous coolant is compressed, whilst a valve maintains a desired pressure level. As the coolant pressure is increased, its enthalpy is raised resulting in a temperature increase. At the high pressure level, the heat is rejected by cooling the gas. Whilst the coolants pressure is lowered, the enthalpy is remained close to constant in the process of decompression. In the evaporator, the coolants enthalpy is increased once more as evaporation takes place under the influence of ambient heat. Whilst the coolant is not evaporated to fully extent, the temperature remains constant.

These processes emerge between four characteristic locations, cp. figure 1.4.

1. Suction line of the compressors
2. Discharge side of the compressors
3. High pressure side of the expansion valve
4. Low pressure side of the expansion valve

Figure 1.4: Idealized transcritical refrigeration process

Figure 1.5: Temperature levels in the gas cooler with the geothermal storage used for sub-cooling.

Starting at the suction line of the compressors, an outline of the cooling unit of *Gimo* ice rink is given below. Cp. figure 1.6 on the facing page.

Compressors Four parallel reciprocating compressors are installed in the *Gimo* ice rink, one of which is frequency controlled in order to adapt the pressure level to the requirements of heating and cooling capacity in the ice rink.

Gas cooling After the discharge side of the compressors, an oil separator (OS1) separates oil and CO₂. Internal heat loads of the ice rink are covered by gas-cooling of CO₂ between the discharge side of the compressors and the high pressure side of the expansion valve. Due to the need for higher temperatures, heat is initially transferred to the heating circuit of the ice rink using an heat exchanger (HX1). Afterwards, the CO₂ is cooled further using a dry cooler, transferring excess heat to the ambient. Eventually, heat can be stored in a ground storage using another heat exchanger (HX2). This enables for further sub-cooling and therefore can potentially increase the system performance. Also, the ground storage temperature level can be regulated this way. Cp. figure 1.5.

Decompression A high pressure valve connects high- and low pressure level. Due to the pressure drop, supercritical CO₂ is transferred into wet steam.

Evaporation In the receiver, liquid- and gaseous CO₂ is separated into the two fractions. The liquid CO₂ is pumped through plastic coated copper tubes which are laid in the concrete under the ice rink slab. On its way through the evaporator, the CO₂ collects heat and the quality rises. However, full evaporation should not take place in the rink tubes. In case the delivered cooling capacity exceeds the needs, cold can also be stored into the geothermal storage. By doing so, the temperature in the geothermal storage and the evaporation process on the cold side of the refrigeration unit can be regulated.

The gaseous CO₂ is sucked in the suction line of the compressors, where a vapour-liquid separator ensures the compressors are fed only with gaseous CO₂ in order to prevent cavitation.

Figure 1.6: Simplified scheme of the cooling unit. Selected sensors and parts of the unit are marked.

Hot water circuit

The hot water circuit is connected to the CO₂ circuit via the heat exchanger *HX1*. The outlet temperature of the heat exchanger 1 on the cold side is controlled to a set point of 60°C .

Cp. figure 1.7 on the facing page.

In the following, the covered heat demands are shown, sorted by decreasing mean temperature level:

1. Hot water (post heating of water of the pre-heater)
2. Dehumidifier
3. Radiators
4. Resurfacing (post heating of water of the pre-heater)
5. Air heating
6. Preheating for hot water and resurfacing demands
7. Freeze protection

Different usages for heat in the facility require different temperature levels, hence the heat is transferred in the shown order using a *water fall* principle. The order of heat supply is arranged in a way that the heat demands are covered while considering optimal temperature levels for each demand. Hot water is used to provide the showers and sinks in the facility with water on the highest temperature level. Hence, a temperature around 60°C close to the temperature set point of the outlet temperature after the heat exchanger 1, is supplied to these loads.

Hot- and re-surfacing water do not form a closed loop, instead they leave the system after being heated up, both demands are covered using a separate piping and tank system. Fresh water is pre-heated using a rather low temperature level in the pre-heater. Afterwards, this water is post-heated to the desired temperature level in the corresponding post-heater. The pre-heater and the two post-heaters are heat storage tanks. As they include considerable amounts of water, they lead to some inertia in the hot water circuit. Hence, the water temperature gradient in the hot water circuit can be positive over these heat storages.

The dehumidifier- and the freeze protection demands have separate circuits as well. In the freeze protection circuit, a mixture of 30% Ethylene-glycol is used in order to avoid freezing of the fluid at the operated temperature level.

Air heating and radiator heat demands are covered using water from the main hot water circuit.

Geothermal storage

The geothermal storage consists of 5 boreholes of a length of 200 meters each. Cp. figure 1.8 on page 13. To avoid freezing of the fluid for low temperatures, a mixture of 30% Ethylene-glycol is used in this circuit.

By transferring heat from the gas cooler into the geothermal storage circuit, it can be used to sub-cool CO₂ on the hot side of the heat exchanger 2 below the ambient air temperature level.

Table 1.1: Heated rooms in the facility (main hall excluded)

Area	Heated area/ m^2
Changing rooms, showers, lockers	436.7
Toilets 1	25.1
Toilets 2	19.7
Storage	36
Sum ^a	517.5

^aAdditional office areas with an area of $36 m^2$ might be used in the future.

The heat exchanger 3 can be used to lower the temperature in the storage circuit by transferring cold of the low pressure side of the cooling unit into the geothermal storage.

Electric loads

The following electric power consumer meters are covered by the data acquisition system:

- Compressors
- Lights
- Geothermal storage pumps
- Hot water pumps
- Liquid CO₂ pump (used to pump CO₂ through the rink floor pipes)
- Dry cooler fans

These power meters cover the main power loads in the facility, however a fraction of the overall power demand remains uncovered. In order to be able to analyse the overall power demand of the facility, electric power consumer data is analysed as well. This data is provided by the community of Östhammar.

Table 1.2: Overview over used power meters and the corresponding consumers in the facility.

ID	Shortcut	Description
E01	AS1	Machine room pumps power consumption: Geothermal storage pump, heating pumps
E02	Lighting	Lighting power consumption in the facility
E03	Dehumidification	Dehumidifier power consumption
PM1	<i>Green and Cool</i> total	Sum of power consumption of PM2, PM3, PM4
PM2	<i>Green and Cool</i> compressors	Compressor power consumption
PM3	<i>Green and Cool</i> circulation	CO ₂ rink floor pump power consumption
PM4	<i>Green and Cool</i> Dry cooler	Dry cooler fan power consumption

Figure 1.8: Simplified scheme of the geothermal storage. Selected parts are marked.

Dehumidifier

For several reasons, the dehumidification of indoor air is important. One aspect is the prevention of mould formations and corrosions, which may occur on cold surfaces. Also, high air humidities over the cold ice surface can lead to fog over the ice sheet. Furthermore, the condensation of water onto the cold ice sheet transfer latent heat into the latter, causing an increased cooling demand.[10]

A dehumidifier Munters MX2-55 is used for the dehumidification of indoor air. This dehumidifier is equipped with a desiccant wheel, that works as a water adsorber for indoor air. This indoor air is blown through one part of the wheel, separated from the second air flow of outdoor air. In order to ensure a continuous adsorption of water and hence, a constant dehumidification, the wheel is rotating. On the upper part of the wheel, an outdoor air flow is absorbing water, recovering the desiccant wheels ability to adsorb water. In order to ensure a proper ability to gather water, this outdoor air is heated up using two energy sources. One is heat from the hot water circuit, referred to as pre-heater. The other is a post-heater, using electric energy. Cp. figure 1.9.

Figure 1.9: Simplified scheme of the dehumidifier.

2 Data processing

Contents

3.1	CO ₂ circuit	24
3.1.1	CO ₂ mass flow in the main circuit	24
3.1.2	Efficiency of the compressors	25
3.1.3	Rejected and recovered heat in the gas cooler	25
3.1.4	Cooling capacity	28
3.1.5	Coefficients of performance	28
3.1.6	Heat recovery ratio	30
3.1.7	Optimal discharge pressure for maximizing the COP	30
3.1.8	Efficiency of the dry cooler	30
3.1.9	System performance with an internal heat exchanger	31
3.1.10	Ice temperature control	34
3.1.11	Rink floor CO ₂ mass flow and –pressure drop	40
3.2	Hot water circuit	43
3.2.1	Efficiency of the heat exchanger 1 (HX1)	44
3.2.2	Hot water circuit heat potential	44
3.3	Geothermal storage circuit	46
3.3.1	Efficiency of the heat exchanger 2	46
3.3.2	Deduced mixture mass flow	46
3.3.3	Geothermal storage ground temperature	47
3.4	Electricity systems	48
3.5	Air properties and dehumidification system	48
3.5.1	Calculation of air properties	48
3.5.2	Dehumidification system	49

2.1 Data acquisition

2.1.1 Working with generated timestamps and derived data

Measurement values are stored on a server and can be downloaded for analysis purposes using a web interface¹. Every measurement value is linked to a corresponding timestamp, both represent a data block. A collection of data blocks is then later referred to as a data set.

In the data acquisition system of the facility, measurement values are not acquired using a constant timing and constant timesteps. Instead, as a sensor receives a new measurement value, a new data block consisting of the measurement value and the corresponding timestamp is stored.

¹Provided by *IWMAC AS*

In order to be able to work with the gathered data of several sensors, timesteps shall be constant and timestamps identical for all data sets. For this reason, a main timestep for the data is generated by re-sampling of the raw data. In advance to the re-sampling of the data, the data is re-indexed, ensuring a minimum resolution for the data. This is not necessary in all cases. However, if there is a data set exhibiting larger periods with a low density of data, this supports a better representation of the raw data by the re-sampled data.

The method of re-sampling consequently results in a certain error, which is referred to as a *re-sampling error*. This error is the greater when the following circumstances add together:

- High gradients between two values following on each other
- Low re-sampling resolutions

In figure 2.1 on the next page, an example of raw data and derived re-sampled data is given. High gradients between two measurement values can lead to high re-sampling errors, as the re-sampled data follows the raw data.

The error resulting from re-sampling the raw data differs according to the data sets of different sensors. To analyse this error and to identify sufficient re-sampling resolutions, data sets of all used sensors have been compared by calculating correlation coefficients for all sensors and different re-sampling resolutions, for both major data samples².

The calculation of correlation coefficients ρ is carried out by using equation (2.2) [16]. The covariance of the raw- and re-sampled data is divided by the product of the standard deviations of the two, in order to norm the correlation coefficient into a range $-1 \leq \rho \leq +1$. Raw data is represented by x , re-sampled data is represented by y .

$$\rho = \frac{COV(x,y)}{\tilde{s}_x \cdot \tilde{s}_y} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\rho = \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (2.2)$$

Apparently, higher re-sampling resolutions increase the correlation coefficients, as the re-sampling error decreases. Depending on the sensor's data set that is used, appropriate re-sampling resolutions shall be selected. Cp. figure 2.2 on page 18.

An overview over the calculated correlation coefficient can be found in the appendix, compare figure ?? on page ?? and figure ?? on page ??.

As can be derived from figure 2.2 on page 18, only for re-sampling resolutions higher than 5 minutes all covered sensors data show correlation coefficients of 0.7 and higher. Hence, a timestep of 1 minute is selected for all calculations. This is particular important, when data is used as a criteria for filtering.

For further details on the data acquisition, cp. section ?? on page ??.

²Cp. section 2.1.2 on page 18

Figure 2.1: Acquired data and generated timestamps with derived data. The resolution of the re-sampled data is low, hence the peak between timestamp 4 and 5 of the raw data is not properly reflected.

Figure 2.2: Correlation coefficients for different re-sampling resolutions for the data sets *Period 1* and *Period 2*.

2.1.2 Analysed measurement periods

Two measurement periods are used, in which two main periods for the analysis of data are defined. This is due to adjustments and the start-up procedure, where the system has not yet been in a stable mode of operation. These main periods are referred to as *Period 1* and *Period 2*. Cp. figure 2.3 on the next page.

- Overall period 1: October 2014 to March 2015
 - Main period 1 (*Period 1*): December 2014 to March 2015
- Overall period 2: July 2015 to December 2015
 - Main period 2 (*Period 2*): August to December 2015

Period 1 covers autumn- and winter conditions, whereas *Period 2* covers summer- to autumn conditions, as well as a wider temperature range. Beside these differences, both periods differ in several aspects. Main differences are described below.

Indoor temperature set point: At the end of November 2014 of *Period 1*, an adjustment for the indoor temperature set point has been carried out. Hence, October and November 2014 are used in the analysed for comparison purposes and are included for the sake of completeness. However, these months are excluded for the major part of the data analysis in *Period 1*. From December 2014 to March 2015 there has been a mostly stable operation without major adjustments of this parameter.

In *Period 2*, the indoor temperature set point has been lowered and the indoor temperature is not kept as constant as in *Period 1*.

Geothermal storage pump: The geothermal storage pump has not been working in *Period 2*.

Dehumidifier: In contrast to *Period 1*, the dehumidifier is used in *Period 2*.

Ice temperature control: In *Period 1*, the ice temperature is controlled using embedded sensors below the ice surface. In *Period 2*, the ice temperature is controlled using an infra-red sensor installed at the ceiling above the ice, pointing on the ice surface.

Figure 2.3: Measurement periods and defined main samples. The period December 2014 to March 2015 is referred to as *Period 1*, while the period August 2015 to December 2015 is referred to as *Period 2*.

As *Period 2* covers 4 months in contrast to 3 months covered in *Period 1*, more data is available in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 2.4 on the following page.

2.1.3 Fluid property

The open source Thermophysical Property Library *CoolProp*[3] is used for the calculation of fluid property for Carbon Dioxide, Water and absolute air humidities. *CoolProps* enables the access to several equations of state³.

To calculate fluid property of the water-ethylene-glycol mixture in the geothermal storage circuit, polynomial equations are used⁴.

2.2 Data visualization

In this thesis, different data visualization techniques are used. Three of these techniques are described in this section:

- Kernel density estimates

³CO₂: [14], water: [18], air: [5]

⁴Cp. [12]

Figure 2.4: Overview over the available amount of data per period.

- Violinplots
- Correlations using quantiles

All three techniques offer the advantage of clarity when working with larger amounts of data. In order to be able to differentiate within a plot, several colours have been defined.

2.2.1 Kernel density estimates

Kernel Density Estimates can be used to replace the actual data points from within a sample by a density curve. In contrast to the technique of a histogram, where the density of the data is drawn using fixed sectors⁵, a Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) is a continuous function. Hence, a KDE can be described as a floating histogram. Cp. figure 2.5 on the next page.

Beside using a KDE to analyse the distribution of one data set, it can also be used to illustrate the distribution of a correlation between two data sets. Cp. figure 2.6 on the facing page.

2.2.2 Violinplots

Violinplots combine a Boxplot with kernel density estimates. This allows to visualize the distribution of larger amounts of data without compromising clarity.

Boxplots illustrate the 25% quantile, the 50% quantile (Median) and the 75% quantile. A commonly used convention is that values exceeding 50% up- and below the 25%– and 75% quantile are considered to be outliers. Outliers are then drawn as single points.

By analysing higher amounts of data within a dataset with a high variability, higher amounts of

⁵Referred to as a *bin*

Figure 2.5: Example of a one dimensional kernel density estimate. The area under the curve equals 1.

Figure 2.6: Example of a two dimensional kernel density estimate.

outliers are then drawn by a Boxplot. As a result, the explanatory power of the illustration is low, as the distribution of data can hardly be distinguished.

As mentioned above, Violinplots cope with the issues of visualizing higher amounts of data by the deviation of a density curve. Cp. figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: Example of a boxplot and a violinplot using the same data sample.

2.2.3 Correlations using quantiles

When correlating two datasets, one dataset represents the values on the abscissa, while the other represents the values on the ordinate. The two datasets form a coordinate system. Using points to visualize every coordinate, it is possible to visualize trends and the distribution of values. Working with larger amounts of data with this kind of visualization of a dataset can result in a loss in significance, when major trends in the data are no longer visible. However, the central tendency of larger amounts of data should be visible, in order to evaluate the correlation. So as to show central tendencies for a correlation, correlations are drawn using quantiles over defined sectors of the data, enabling the illustration of these tendencies. Cp. figure 2.8 on the facing page. The significance of the exhibited trends depend on the amount of data in each sector. Hence the distribution of the available data is fundamental when it comes to the evaluation of the shown trends.

In addition to the illustration of the trends in the underlying data, the calculated quantiles are partly used for curve fitting of a regression line. The advantage of this over using the raw data is that a regression over quantiles is insensitive to outliers. Outliers are values that do not dispose the relationship between the two variables in contrast to the major amount of evaluated data. The deduced relationship between the two variables using a regression over the median can then be used to predict

Figure 2.8: Example for correlations using quantiles over defined sectors.

3 Calculation of operating parameters and specific system studies

Contents

4.1	Basic energy data	50
4.2	Basic power data of the cooling unit	55
4.3	Indoor- and ambient air conditions	62
4.4	General system performance	66
4.5	System behaviour	68
4.5.1	Influence of ambient conditions	68
4.5.2	Influence of indoor conditions	75
4.5.3	Load dependencies	75
4.6	Components	82
4.6.1	Dry cooler performance	82
4.6.2	Compressors	82
4.6.3	Dehumidification system	84
4.7	Subsystems	88
4.7.1	Hot water circuit	88
	Efficiency of the heat exchanger <i>HX1</i>	90
	Hot water circuit heat potential	95
4.7.2	Geothermal storage	98
	Efficiency of the heat exchanger <i>HX2</i>	100
4.7.3	Electricity systems	102

As operating parameters are calculated using measurement values of several sensors, it is assumed that for each timestamp all measurements are valid to calculate the appropriate operating parameter. An uncertainty arises from this assumption, which is considered to be small for most cases.

3.1 CO₂ circuit

3.1.1 CO₂ mass flow in the main circuit

As there is no direct measurement of the CO₂ mass- or volume flow available, the CO₂ mass flow is deduced using an energy balance over the compressors¹.

Since the compressors are semi-hermetic, it is assumed that the overall motor losses of the compressors are negligible, as they remain inside the compressor cabinet and do not cross the balance

¹Cp. also [4]

Figure 3.1: Energy balance over the compressor. As all used compressors are semi-hermetic, losses of the motors are considered to remain in the compressor casing.

border. They are considered to be part of the energy transferred to CO₂. Heat losses of the compressors are considered to be 7% of the compressor power consumption, cp. equation (3.2). The compressor power P_{comp} is gathered using the power meter PM2. Cp. figure 3.1.

$$\dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{P_{\text{el,comp}} - \dot{Q}_{\text{loss}}}{\epsilon_{\text{comp}}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{P_{\text{el,comp}} \cdot (1 - 0.07)}{h_2 - h_1} \quad (3.2)$$

3.1.2 Efficiency of the compressors

The isentropic efficiency is used to analyse the compressor efficiency distribution.

The fraction of electric power that is transformed into compression work is related to the specific isentropic compression work. By utilizing the rule of proportion, the total isentropic efficiency over the compressors is calculated using the relation of specific isentropic compression work and real specific compression work. Cp. equation (3.3) [7, pp. 56,77] and figure 3.2 on the following page.

$$\eta_{\text{total}} = \frac{\epsilon_{\text{comp,is}}}{\epsilon_{\text{comp}}} = \frac{h_{2,\text{is}} - h_1}{h_2 - h_1} \quad (3.3)$$

3.1.3 Rejected and recovered heat in the gas cooler

On the high pressure side, CO₂ is cooled in the gas cooler. There are three points in the gas cooler, where heat can be rejected from the CO₂ circuit:

- Heat exchanger 1 (Thermal connection to the hot water circuit)

Figure 3.2: Real specific compression work ϵ_{comp} and ideal specific isentropic compression work $\epsilon_{\text{comp,is}}$.

- Dry cooler (Thermal connection to the ambient)
- Heat exchanger 2 (Thermal connection to the geothermal storage)

Cp. figure 3.3 on page 28 and figure 3.4 on page 29.

Depending on whether both heat exchangers of the geothermal storage are used, the geothermal storage can be either counted as part of the heat recovery system or as a simple heat sink.

For the calculation of rejected heat to the hot water circuit, two temperature sensors ($TT1$, $TT40$) and the pressure sensor of the high pressure level ($PT1$) are used. The specific enthalpy before and after the heat exchanger $HX1$ is calculated utilizing the *Thermophysical Property Library Coolprop*².

By the multiplication of enthalpy difference over the heat exchanger and the CO_2 mass flow, the rejected heat to the hot water circuit is calculated. Cp. equation (3.6).

$$h_2 = f(\vartheta_{TT1}, P_{PT1}) \quad (3.4)$$

$$h_{TT40} = f(\vartheta_{TT40}, P_{PT1}) \quad (3.5)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{hw, rejected}} = (h_{TT40} - h_2) \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (3.6)$$

Regarding the geothermal storage circuit, rather than calculating the rejected heat, the absorbed heat in this circuit is calculated. This is due to the fact that the inlet temperature on the warm side of the heat exchanger $HX2$ can not be determined continuously:

²Cp. section 2.1.3 on page 19

$$\vartheta_{\text{HX2, CO}_2, \text{ in}} = \begin{cases} \vartheta_{\text{TT40}}, & \text{if } \text{MV1} \equiv 100 \\ \vartheta_{\text{TT2:1}}, & \text{if } \text{MV1} \equiv 0 \\ \text{undefined}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.7)$$

In order to calculate the absorbed heat in the geothermal storage circuit, the mean heat capacity of the mixture is calculated, using the mean temperature on the cold side, cp. equation (3.8b).

$$\bar{c}_{p, \text{ mix.}} = f(\vartheta_{\text{HX2}}/2) \quad (3.8a)$$

$$\bar{c}_{p, \text{ mix.}} = f((\vartheta_{\text{TT20}} - \vartheta_{\text{TT19}})/2) \quad (3.8b)$$

The absorbed heat in the geothermal storage circuit is then calculated using equation (3.9b).

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{geo, absorbed}} = \dot{m}_{\text{mix}} \cdot \bar{c}_{p, \text{ mix.}} \cdot \Delta\vartheta_{\text{HX2}} \quad (3.9a)$$

$$= \dot{m}_{\text{mix}} \cdot \bar{c}_{p, \text{ mix.}} \cdot (\vartheta_{\text{TT20}} - \vartheta_{\text{TT19}}) \quad (3.9b)$$

Since the temperature sensor *TT2:1* is placed at the dry cooler outlet, heat that is rejected to the ambient using the dry cooler ($\dot{Q}_{\text{dc, rejected}}$) can only be deduced when the bypass valve *MV1* is completely opened to the bypass side. Only for this case, the CO_2 mass flow through the dry cooler is known.

As a work-around and simplification to this difficulty, $\dot{Q}_{\text{dc, rejected}}$ is calculated using the difference of the main rejected heat in the gas cooler, the rejected heat into the hot water circuit and the absorbed heat of the geothermal storage. Thus, the rejected heat by the dry cooler can be calculated continuously, cp. equation (3.13).

$$h_2 = f(\vartheta_{\text{TT1}}, P_{\text{PT1}}) \quad (3.10)$$

$$h_3 = f(\vartheta_{\text{TT2}}, P_{\text{PT1}}) \quad (3.11)$$

$$\dot{Q}_1 = (h_3 - h_2) \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2} \quad (3.12)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{dc, rejected}} = \dot{Q}_1 - \dot{Q}_{\text{hw, rejected}} - \dot{Q}_{\text{geo, absorbed}} \quad (3.13)$$

One downside of this simplification is that the losses in the gas cooler are excluded. Another issue that arises from this is the exclusion of inertia of the system. There are cases where the sum of rejected heat to the hot water- and geothermal storage circuit exceed the overall rejected heat in the gas cooler. In these cases, the calculated rejected heat from the gas cooler is negative.

By definition, all calculated heats in the gas cooler are positive numbers. Hence in the mentioned cases, the calculated rejected heat by the gas cooler is set to equal zero.

Figure 3.3: Rejected– and recovered heat on the high pressure level of the cooling unit. This part of the CO₂ circuit is referred to as the gas cooler.

3.1.4 Cooling capacity

The main cooling capacity \dot{Q}_0 is calculated using the enthalpy difference between the compressor suction side (h_1) and the discharge side of the high pressure valve (h_4):

$$h_1 = f(\vartheta_{TT5}, P_{PT3}) \quad (3.14)$$

$$h_4 = f(\vartheta_{TT1}, P_{PT1}) = h_3 \quad (3.15)$$

$$\dot{Q}_0 = (h_1 - h_4) \cdot \dot{m}_{CO_2} \quad (3.16)$$

As it has been recognized by Energi & Kylanalys, the pressure sensor *PT2* delivers defective values. Because it is placed at the suction side of the compressors at the position of lowest pressure in the main CO₂ circuit, it is expected to show smaller measurement values compared to the pressure sensor *PT3*, which is placed directly after the expansion valve. However, *PT2* shows higher measurement values, cp. table 3.1. Hence, the sensor *PT3* is used for the low pressure level.

Table 3.1: Comparison of measurement values of the pressure sensors *PT2* and *PT3*.

Period		Sensor	
		PT2	PT3
1	Mean	29.33	28.88
	Median	29.26	28.8
2	Mean	29.064	28.79
	Median	29.26	28.96

3.1.5 Coefficients of performance

The coefficient of performance for the cooling performance COP_0 , as well as for the heating performance COP_1 of the refrigeration system, are calculated using equation (3.17) on the next page

Figure 3.4: Gas cooling section in the refrigeration unit.

and equation (3.18).

The sum of electric power consume of the compressors P_{comp} and auxiliary power consume P_{aux} is recorded using the power meter PMI^3 .

$$COP_0 = \frac{\dot{Q}_0}{P_{el} + P_{aux}} = \frac{(h_1 - h_4) \cdot \dot{m}_{CO_2}}{P_{el,comp} + P_{aux}} \quad (3.17)$$

$$COP_1 = \frac{\dot{Q}_1}{P_{el} + P_{aux}} = \frac{(h_2 - h_3) \cdot \dot{m}_{CO_2}}{P_{el,comp} + P_{aux}} \quad (3.18)$$

The global coefficient of performance is calculated using equation (3.19).

$$COP_{\text{global}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{hw,rejected}} + \dot{Q}_0}{P_{el,comp} + P_{aux}} \quad (3.19)$$

³Cp. section 3.4 on page 48 about the methodology of the electricity system.

3.1.6 Heat recovery ratio

The heat recovery ratio is the relation of the recovered heat and the cooling capacity. In an ice rink, in which both recovered heat as well as cooling capacity are important, this can be a useful figure in order to judge the system performance.

$$\text{HRR} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{HW}}}{\dot{Q}_0} \quad (3.20)$$

3.1.7 Optimal discharge pressure for maximizing the COP

It is proposed by Prof. Dr. Samer Sawalha in his dissertation, that the system performance can be optimized using a discharge pressure controlled as a function of the temperature after the heat recovery heat exchanger *HXI* $\vartheta_{\text{HR,exit}}$. This yields a maximization of the coefficients of performance COP_0 and COP_1 . The optimal discharge pressure for a maximization of these COP is calculated using the following equation[17, p. 51].

$$P_{\text{disch,opt}} = 2.7 \cdot \vartheta_{\text{HR,exit}} - 6 \text{ [bar]} \quad (3.21)$$

This heat recovery exit temperature is measured by the sensor TT40 after the heat exchanger *HXI*

$$(3.22)$$

$$P_{\text{disch,opt}} = 2.7 \cdot \vartheta_{\text{TT40}} - 6 \text{ [bar]} \quad (3.23)$$

This calculated optimal discharge pressure can be used for the comparison with the actual measured discharge pressure. An optimization potential can then be identified.

3.1.8 Efficiency of the dry cooler

The efficiency of the dry cooler is calculated using 3 temperature sensors, in case the dry cooler bypass valve *MVI* is fully opened to the dry cooler bypass:

- Dry cooler inlet temperature ϑ_{TT40}
- Dry cooler outlet temperature $\vartheta_{\text{TT2:1}}$
- Ambient temperature $\vartheta_{\text{ambient}}$

$$\eta_{\text{dc}} = \begin{cases} \frac{\vartheta_{\text{TT40}} - \vartheta_{\text{TT2:1}}}{\vartheta_{\text{TT40}} - \vartheta_{\text{ambient}}}, & \text{if } \text{MV1} \equiv 100 \\ \text{undefined}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.24)$$

3.1.9 System performance with an internal heat exchanger

An internal heat exchanger enables for a transfer of heat from one position of the refrigeration unit to another. Different position are possible for such heat exchange. In this case, an internal heat exchanger from the end of the gas cooler to the end of the low pressure side of the cooling unit is chosen. In the latter, the internal heat exchanger is also referred to as *IHX*. Cp. figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5: Cooling unit with an internal heat exchanger at the end of the gas cooler and the suction line of the compressors.

In order to evaluate the effect of an internal heat exchanger to the system performance, two main scenarios are considered and compared:

- Reference scenario (existing system set-up)
- Internal heat exchanger scenario

By using an internal heat exchanger in the system at the described position, the entry enthalpy to the high pressure valve at the end of the gas cooler can be lowered, while the entry enthalpy to the compressors is increased. This leads to a higher enthalpy spread over the gas cooler and evaporator. Hence, the available cooling capacity is increased provided that the refrigerant mass flow is not altered. In order to meet the measured cooling demand, the CO₂ mass flow and therefore the compressor power demand can be lowered, compared to the reference scenario. Cp. figure 3.6 on the following page.

The effect of an internal heat exchanger on the system behaviour is the greater, the higher the efficiency of this heat exchanger is. As the efficiency of the internal heat exchanger is not known,

Figure 3.6: Reference– and internal heat exchanger cycle compared. Pressure levels are maintained the same in both cases, the efficiency of the internal heat exchanger η_{IHX} equals 40% in this example.

a range of efficiency coefficients η_{IHX} from 10% to 90% is considered.

The outlet temperatures of the warm- and cold side of the heat exchanger are calculated using equation (3.25) and equation (3.26).

$$\vartheta_{IHX,out(w)} = \vartheta_{IHX,in(w)} - \eta_{IHX} \cdot (\vartheta_{IHX,in(w)} - \vartheta_{IHX,in(c)}) \quad (3.25)$$

$$\vartheta_{IHX,out(c)} = \vartheta_{IHX,in(c)} + \eta_{IHX} \cdot (\vartheta_{IHX,in(w)} - \vartheta_{IHX,in(c)}) \quad (3.26)$$

It is assumed that the enthalpy lift to CO_2 caused by the compressive work in the *IHX* scenario equals the compressive work in the reference scenario:

$$\Delta h_{\text{comp},IHX} = \Delta h_{\text{comp},\text{ref}} \quad (3.27)$$

The new rejected heat in the gas cooler $\dot{Q}_{1,IHX,\text{ref}}$ and the new cooling capacity $\dot{Q}_{0,IHX,\text{ref}}$ are then calculated with the reference CO_2 mass flow:

$$\dot{Q}_{1,IHX,\text{ref}} = (h_{2,IHX} - h_{3,IHX,\text{in}}) \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{ref}} \quad (3.28)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{0,IHX,\text{ref}} = (h_1 - h_{4,IHX}) \cdot \dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2,\text{ref}} \quad (3.29)$$

To meet the cooling demand of the reference scenario, a new CO_2 mass flow is calculated, as well as the new available heat in the gas cooler. Cp. equation (3.32) on the next page.

$$\dot{Q}_{0,IHX,set} = \dot{Q}_{0,ref} \quad (3.30)$$

$$\dot{m}_{CO_2,IHX,set} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{0,IHX,set}}{(h_1 - h_{4,IHX})} \quad (3.31)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{1,IHX,set} = (h_{2,IHX} - h_{3,IHX}) \cdot \dot{m}_{CO_2,IHX,set} \quad (3.32)$$

As a consequence of the reduced CO₂ mass flow, the compressor power demand is decreased. In order to be able to calculate this new compressor power demand, the latter is correlated to the CO₂ mass flow. It is assumed that the pressure difference on both sides of the internal heat exchanger equals zero, in order to maintain the working point of the compressors and to be able to predict the behaviour of the latter with a lower load. The expected behaviour of the dependency of CO₂ mass flow and compressor power demand is linear, intersecting the origin of the graph. The expected behaviour is met. Cp. figure 3.7.

Figure 3.7: Correlation of compressor power demand and CO₂ mass flow.
(Data: Period 1 and Period 2)

The regression coefficient of this correlation is determined:

$$\frac{P_{comp}}{\dot{m}_{CO_2}} = 70.78 \frac{kW \cdot s}{kg} \quad (3.33)$$

A new compressor power demand is then calculated using the regression coefficient:

$$P_{comp,IHX,set} = 70.78 \cdot \dot{m}_{CO_2,IHX,set} \quad (3.34)$$

As a consequence of the decreased CO₂ mass flow and the altered exit enthalpy at the discharge side of the compressors, the available heat for heat recovery purposes is re-calculated. It is assumed that the exit enthalpy of the heat recovery heat exchanger (HX1) equals the exit enthalpy at this point in the reference scenario:

$$\dot{Q}_{hw,rejected} = (h_{2,IHX} - h_{HX1,out(w)}) \cdot \dot{m}_{CO_2} \quad (3.35)$$

3.1.10 Ice temperature control

The ice temperature can be measured with two embedded sensors below the ice surface, or with an infra-red sensor installed below the ceiling and pointing on the ice from above. In *Period 1*, the ice temperature is controlled using one embedded sensor in the ice sheet. At that time, the two embedded sensors were the only available sensors for a direct measurement of the ice temperature. In *Period 2* however, an infra-red sensor is used for the control of the ice temperature⁴.

In order to compare the two control strategies, an embedded sensor is used, as in both periods, measurements of these sensors are available. Comparing the two embedded sensors, *Embedded 2* exhibits a stronger response to a temperature change of the ice sheet caused by re-surfacings. Thus, this sensor is used for comparisons of the two control strategies. Cp. figure 3.8.

Figure 3.8: Ice temperature sensor signal comparison. In *Period 1*, the ice temperature is controlled using an embedded sensor in the ice sheet. In *Period 2*, an infra-red sensor mounted below the ceiling and pointing on the ice sheet, is used. Hence, the infra-red sensor measures the ice surface temperature.

Both measurement principles differ from each other, and so do the resulting signals of the two sensors. As the ice temperature deviates from the set point, the control adapts the working point of the compressors. Cooling capacity, heat gains and heat losses into the ice sheet have to be kept in balance in order to maintain a certain ice temperature. The main reason for peaks in heat gains to the ice sheet are re-surfacings, resulting in a deviation of the ice temperature from the set point.

By comparison, the reactivity of the infra-red sensor is significantly higher. Furthermore, the infra-red sensor shows a cleaner signal for periods of small changes in ice temperature. The embedded sensors however exhibit an oscillating behaviour. In relation to measured peak temperatures, these oscillations are rather high. This leads to a need to smooth out the measurement signal, in order to avoid these oscillations to be proceeded to the compressor control. One reason for relatively low peak temperature during re-surfacings is the inertia caused by the ice sheet. In summary, oscillations in the control loop can be reduced using the infra-red sensor, while a stronger response to an ice temperature increase is ensured with this sensor.

The ice temperature set point using the embedded sensor is -4.5°C . However, using the infra-red sensor, only the ice surface temperature can be measured. Hence, the settled ice temperature at the measurement position of *Embedded 2* is rather around -4.7°C with the infra-red sensor control and the used adjustments of this control-loop.

⁴Cp. section 2.1.2 on page 18 about the two analysed periods. Cp. also figure ?? on page ??.

There are different aspects that can be used to quantify advantages and disadvantages of the two control strategies:

- Maximum deviation of the ice temperature from its set point
- Time needed to stabilize the ice temperature back on its set point
- Energy needed to stabilize the ice temperature back on its set point

These aspects are analysed with an algorithm. This algorithm uses several parameters in order to trace re-surfacings and enabling an analysis and evaluation of the two control strategies.

As the embedded sensor *Embedded 2* exhibits a scattered signal, a rolling mean rm_5 is used in order to smooth the measurement signal. This rolling mean is calculated using a window of 5 values, corresponding to a mean over 5 minutes for a time step of 1 minute. Another rolling mean rm_{30} is used as lower reference value, including 30 values into the calculation. This corresponds to a mean over half an hour.

$$rm_5 = [\bar{v}_{\text{embedded } 2}]_{\text{window}=15} \quad (3.36)$$

$$rm_{30} = [\bar{v}_{\text{embedded } 2}]_{\text{window}=30} \quad (3.37)$$

The difference of the two calculated rolling means is used as criterion to trace re-surfacings:

$$\Delta rm = rm_5 - rm_{30} \quad (3.38)$$

If a re-surfacing is traced, several values are stored. These values can later on be used to evaluate the re-surfacing:

- The elapsed time, ρ_{resurf_i}
- The maximum temperature deviation from the set point
- The elapsed time from the point of maximum temperature deviation and end of the re-surfacing, ρ_{2,resurf_i}
- Using the mean power over the observed individual re-surfacing and ρ_{resurf_i} , the observed cooling capacity is stored as an energy
- A characterization of a re-surfacing depending on the termination criterion: Either Δrm is positive once more, or the corresponding set point is reached:
 - Embedded sensor: -4.4°C
 - Infra-red sensor: -4.6°C

Cp. figure 3.9 on page 37.

Several re-surfacings coming after each other lead to an increase in the ice temperature. This increase is dependant on several factors, one of which is the time in between two re-surfacings. This time interval, among other factors, is not maintained constant over the two periods. Thus, it is difficult to make comparison on them by using the whole amount of traced re-surfacings. For that reason, only re-surfacings that lead to a stabilization on the corresponding ice temperature set point are used in the comparison. These re-surfacings are selected based on the defined termination criteria. Cp. figure 3.10 on page 38 and figure 3.11 on page 39.

The heat demand from the re-surfacer hot water supply can not be used to trace re-surfacings, as a buffer is used within the hot water supply. This leads to a delay, after which the actual heat demand of the re-surfacer gets visible in the hot water circuit. Cp. figure 3.12 on page 39

Figure 3.9: Program flow chart of the used algorithm for the evaluation of re-surfacing control strategies.

Figure 3.10: Detail of a day with traced re-surfacings by the algorithm in *Period 1* (Ice temperature controlled by the embedded sensor).

Figure 3.11: Detail of a day with traced re-surfacings by the algorithm in *Period 2* (Ice temperature controlled by the infra-red sensor).

Figure 3.12: Response of ice temperature sensors and measured heat demand of the re-surfacer.

3.1.11 Rink floor CO₂ mass flow and –pressure drop

The working point of the pump is defined by the pressure drop in the rink floor tubes and pump specifications. In case of Gimo this pressure drop is below the pressure range specified by the manufacturer. While this can potentially be an issue for the pump itself due to the risk of cavitation, the related CO₂ mass flow in the rink floor tubes is unknown.

The CO₂ pump is capacity controlled proportional to the compressor power and therefore indirectly linked to the cooling capacity. The correlation of the rink pump signal to the compressor power demand shows a linear behaviour in *Period 1*. Same applies to *Period 2*, however in this period, runaway values can be observed. Cp. figure 3.13.

Figure 3.13: Density of correlated data of the rink pump signal and the compressor power demand.

These runaway values are caused by an issue with the control of the pump, as the pump was partly locked at a rink pump signal of 100% in *Period 2*. As the compressor power in *Period 2* covers a wider range, the rink pump signal covers a wider range in this period as well. Hence, data of *Period 2* is also included in this analysis, while runaway values are excluded. In order to do so, a major tendency in the data is identified using median values of defined sectors. The dependency of the rink pump signal on the compressor power is considered to be a linear function. The median

values are then used for the deviation of a linear regression model. Subsequently, values are filtered using the linear regression and a confidence interval of $\pm 10\%$ of rink pump signal around the linear regression function. This filtered data provides a basis for the following analysis. Cp. figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14: Correlation between rink pump signal and compressor power demand. The regression is calculated using median values of defined sectors of data. Values are filtered using the linear regression and a confidence interval of $\pm 10\%$.
(Data: *Period 1* and *Period 2*)

In normal operation conditions, CO_2 is still liquid to some extent when leaving the rink pump tubes. Hence, a quality smaller 1 of CO_2 leaving the rink floor tubes can be observed in most cases. For these conditions, evaporation temperature and –pressure are close to constant over the area of evaporation. Consequently, the evaporator exit enthalpy can not be determined for these conditions. However, in case a re–surfacing offsets the system from its former working point in such way that super–heating of CO_2 occurs, the enthalpy at the end of the rink floor tubes can be determined. A super–heated CO_2 temperature of at least 3 Kelvin is considered as a criteria in order to filter for the deduction of CO_2 rink floor mass flow. Cp. equation (3.40) on the following page.

$$\dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{rink}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_0}{\Delta h_{\text{rink}}} \quad (3.39)$$

The CO₂ rink mass flow is calculated using the overall cooling capacity \dot{Q}_0 and the enthalpy difference of CO₂ in the rink floor tubes return and unsaturated liquid enthalpy of the low pressure level:

$$\dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2, \text{rink}} = \frac{\dot{Q}_0}{(h_{\text{rink return}} - h(p_{\text{low}}, Q = 0))} \quad (3.40)$$

Figure 3.15: Main- and rink floor CO₂ circuit in the pressure-enthalpy diagram.

3.2 Hot water circuit

The heat demands in the hot water circuit are calculated using a water mass flow and the temperatures at appropriate positions. With the enthalpy difference between two measurement points and the water mass flow, the heat demands are calculated. Resulting from the inertia of the measurements, the calculated heat demands can be negative. Cp. figure 3.16.

Figure 3.16: Measurement points in the hot water circuit.

The water mass flow is derived using the measured water volume flow and the calculated density ρ_{H_2O} . The density is calculated using the following parameters.

- An assumed water pressure of $P_{H_2O} = 101325 Pa^5$
- The temperature sensor signal $VPIGT1$ as water temperature $\vartheta_{H_2O, VPI-GT1}$, installed close to the water volume flow measurement position $VPI-VMM1$

$$\rho_{H_2O} = F(P_{H_2O}, \vartheta_{H_2O, VPI-GT1}) \quad (3.41)$$

The calculated density is then used to calculate the water mass flow:

$$\dot{m}_{H_2O} = \rho_{H_2O} \cdot \dot{V}_{H_2O} \quad (3.42)$$

$$\dot{m}_{H_2O} = \rho_{H_2O} \cdot \dot{V}_{H_2O} \quad (3.43)$$

⁵According to the normal temperature and pressure (NTP) standard.

3.2.1 Efficiency of the heat exchanger 1 (HX1)

The efficiency of the heat exchanger *HX1* is calculated using 3 temperature sensors, provided that the bypass valve *MV2* is completely opened:

- *HX1* inlet temperature on the warm side ϑ_{TT1}
- *HX1* outlet temperature on the warm side ϑ_{TT40}
- *HX1* inlet temperature on the cold side $\vartheta_{KA1TT42}$

$$\eta_{HX1} = \begin{cases} (\vartheta_{TT1} - \vartheta_{TT40}) / (\vartheta_{TT1} - \vartheta_{KA1TT42}), & \text{if } MV2 \equiv 100 \\ \text{undefined,} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.44)$$

In case the bypass valve *MV2* is closed, a calculation of this efficiency is not possible.

3.2.2 Hot water circuit heat potential

The available heat in the hot water circuit can be increased, when the lower temperature level $\vartheta_{HX1,c,in}$ of the hot water circuit is lowered. This way, the enthalpy difference between heat exchanger inlet– and outlet is increased on both sides, resulting in an increase in transferred power. Furthermore, the volume flow \dot{V}_{hw} in this circuit can be increased. The high temperature level of this circuit however has to remain on at least 60°C, in order to consider the requested temperature set point⁶.

Figure 3.17: Water mass flow distribution in the hot water circuit.

To evaluate the heat potential of this circuit, two different scenarios are covered. The measured data is referred to as the reference case.

⁶To avoid the formation of Legionella bacteria in process water.

Scenario 1:

- The volume flow is kept as in the reference case
- The lower temperature level is decreased step-wise from 30.0°C to 7.5°C

Scenario 2:

- The volume flow is kept on a constantly high level of 1.9 kg/s
- The lower temperature level is decreased step-wise from 30.0°C to 7.5°C

For both scenarios, it is assumed that the high temperature level can be maintained on the set-point of 60°C, regardless of the increased enthalpy spread and the increased water volume flow in the second scenario. Furthermore, it is assumed that all heat consumers in the circuit can maintain their performance as in the reference case.

3.3 Geothermal storage circuit

3.3.1 Efficiency of the heat exchanger 2

The efficiency of the heat exchanger $HX2$ is calculated using 3 temperature sensors:

- $HX2$ inlet temperature on the warm side ϑ_{TT40}
- $HX2$ inlet temperature on the cold side ϑ_{TT19}
- $HX2$ outlet temperature on the cold side ϑ_{TT20}

Also, the geothermal storage pump signal and the bypass valve $MV1$ are used as criteria. The efficiency is only calculated provided that the geothermal pump $KB1-P1$ is running. Another criterion for the calculation of this efficiency is the set point of the bypass valve $MV1$. Only if it is either completely opened or closed, the inlet temperature on the warm side of the heat exchanger can be determined. As the temperature sensors $TT40$ and $TT2:1$ do not display the actual warm side heat exchanger inlet temperature short after the valve has switched its value, a certain error results from this.

$$\eta_{HX2} = \begin{cases} (\vartheta_{TT20} - \vartheta_{TT19}) / (\vartheta_{TT40} - \vartheta_{TT19}), & \text{if } KB1-P1 > 0, MV1 \equiv 100 \\ (\vartheta_{TT20} - \vartheta_{TT19}) / (\vartheta_{TT2:1} - \vartheta_{TT19}), & \text{if } KB1-P1 > 0, MV1 \equiv 0 \\ \text{undefined,} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.45)$$

3.3.2 Deduced mixture mass flow

In the geothermal storage, a mixture of 70% water and 30% glycol is used, in order to ensure a considerable anti-freeze protection.

The inlet temperature of the heat exchanger 2 is only known for either fully closed- or fully opened bypass valve $MV1$, cp. equation (3.46). Hence, the enthalpy difference of the warm side of the heat exchanger 2 is only calculated for these two cases.

$$\Delta h_{HX2,CO_2} = \begin{cases} h_{TT40} - h_{TT2}, & \text{if } MV1 \equiv 100 \\ h_{TT2:1} - h_{TT2}, & \text{if } MV1 \equiv 0 \\ \text{undefined,} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.46)$$

The mixture mass flow is deduced if the criteria are met:

$$\dot{Q}_{geo,rejected} \cdot \eta_{HX2} = \dot{Q}_{geo,absorbed} \quad (3.47a)$$

$$\dot{m}_{CO_2} \cdot \Delta h_{HX2,CO_2} \cdot \eta_{HX2} = \dot{m}_{mix} \cdot c_{p,mix} \cdot \Delta \vartheta_{HX2,mix} \quad (3.47b)$$

$$\dot{m}_{mix} = \frac{\dot{m}_{CO_2} \cdot \Delta h_{HX2,CO_2} \cdot \eta_{HX2}}{c_{p,mix} \cdot \Delta \vartheta_{HX2,mix}} \quad (3.47c)$$

The resulting distribution of values is illustrated in figure 3.18. Values of the mixture mass flow below a geothermal pump signal σ of 20% are excluded. Below this threshold, the deduced pattern of values deviates from the expected function. This expected function is quadratic, intersecting a water–glycol mass flow at 0 for a pump signal of 0.

While values $0 \leq \sigma \leq 69$ show the expected quadratic behaviour, a limit for the mass flow is reached above $\sigma \approx 69$. Above this value, the mass flow is not increasing when the pump signal is increased.

Figure 3.18: Deduced water–glycol mass flow. Values below a pump signal of 20% deviate from the expected function and are excluded from the regression (marked white). The error bars show the 75%– and 25% quantile.

As the quadratic model is build using median points of the correlation between deduced mixture mass flow and geothermal pump signal, the model can be used to predict median values of the mixture mass flow in the geothermal storage circuit. However, it has to be kept in mind that simplifications apply to this method.

In order to deduce meaningful mixture mass flow values, the system has to be kept in a close to in–transient state. This way, every temperature sensor keeps a similar signal over a reasonable amount of time.

3.3.3 Geothermal storage ground temperature

The geothermal storage circuit return temperature can be used to analyse the ground temperature. It has to be kept in mind while opting for this temperature, that this temperature is influenced by several phenomena. It represents the actual ground temperature only after being settled in the storage for a reasonable time, when the fluid temperature does only change to small amount per time.

3.4 Electricity systems

The power consume measured by the community and the measurements in the facility differ from each other. The reason is that there are power consumers in the facility that are not recorded. This power consume is accounted to a consumer group *Miscellaneous*.

The power meter *E02* includes a base load which is considered to be part of the group *Miscellaneous*. When lights are switched off, this base load of *E02* becomes visible. Cp. figure 3.19.

Table 3.2: Light signal and corresponding values of the power meter *E02* compared.

Light signal/%	E02/kW
0	2
50	5
100	10

Figure 3.19: Energy meter *E02*, power consumer behaviour.

3.5 Air properties and dehumidification system

3.5.1 Calculation of air properties

The absolute air humidity is a measure with significance in order to judge the performance of the dehumidification system. The absolute air humidity ρ_w is calculated for indoor- and ambient air. For the calculation, the corresponding temperatures and relative humidity measures are used, as well as an assumed constant air pressure of 101325Pa.

$$\rho_{w,indoor} = F(\vartheta_{indoor}, \phi_{indoor}, p_{air}) \quad (3.48)$$

$$\rho_{w,ambient} = F(\vartheta_{ambient}, \phi_{ambient}, p_{air}) \quad (3.49)$$

For the calculation of air properties, the open source Thermophysical Property Library CoolProp⁷ is used.

3.5.2 Dehumidification system

For the analysis of the dehumidification system⁸, the efficiency of the water–air heat exchanger *HXDehum* in the dehumidification system is calculated:

$$\eta_{\text{hx,dehum}} = \frac{\vartheta_{\text{hx,dehum,in(w)}} - \vartheta_{\text{hx,dehum,out(w)}}}{\vartheta_{\text{hx,dehum,in(w)}} - \vartheta_{\text{ambient}}} \quad (3.50)$$

Using this heat exchanger efficiency, the pre–heater outlet temperature $\vartheta_{\text{dehum,preheat}}$ is calculated:

$$\vartheta_{\text{dehum,preheat}} = \eta_{\text{hx,dehum}} \cdot (\vartheta_{\text{hx,dehum,in(w)}} - \vartheta_{\text{ambient}}) + \vartheta_{\text{ambient}} \quad (3.51)$$

Cp. figure 3.20.

Figure 3.20: Simplified scheme of the dehumidifier.

⁷Cp. section 2.1.3 on page 19 about CoolProp.

⁸Cp. also figure ?? on page ?? for an image of the dehumidifier.

4 General system analysis

Contents

5.1	Heat demand for additional heated space	109
5.2	Monitoring system COP calculation	109
5.3	System performance with an internal heat exchanger	109
5.4	Rink floor	113
5.4.1	Ice temperature control	113
5.4.2	CO ₂ rink mass flow and –pressure drop	117

4.1 Basic energy data

October 2014 - March 2015 (Period 1)

At the end of November in the winter period 2014 and 2015 (*Period 1*), the system control has been adapted. When comparing data of these first two months to other months, this should be considered.

The major demand for electric energy in the facility accounts to compressive work with a monthly demand of around 30MWh in this first period. The second highest demand has been lights, with a monthly demand of around 10MWh. Cp. figure 4.1 on page 52.

On the warm side of the unit, rejected heat into the hot water circuit accounts to 70–75MWh in the first two months. In December 2014 and January 2015, this heat quantity accounts to around 90MWh. In February and March 2015, values of 80 and 85MWh can be observed for this heat. The rejected heat into the ambient by the dry cooler has been around 30–38MWh in the first two months and around 20–25MWh in the following months. Absorbed heat in the geothermal storage accounts to around 5-7 MWh over the whole winter period. The provided cold of the unit has been around 70-80 MWh.

The visible difference between the first two months October and November to the rest of the winter period can be caused to some extent by the noted adaptations at the beginning of this section, and to some extent by the influence of ambient conditions on the system. Cp. figure 4.2 on page 53.

In the hot water circuit, the major fraction accounts for air heating. The second highest demand accounts for the radiators. In this period, the dehumidifier has only been used for test purposes in November 2014 and has been working normally at the end of March 2015. Cp. figure 4.3 on page 54.

August 2015 - December 2015 (Period 2)

Regarding the electric demands in the facility, it is conspicuous that the dehumidifier has been the second highest demand after the compressors in August and September. In the rest of this period, the demand for the dehumidifier has been lower than the demand for lighting, which is the second highest demand in this period.

In *Period 2*, the geothermal pump has not been working. Hence, all excess heat potential remaining against the ambient temperature in the gas cooler has been rejected to the ambient by the dry cooler. In August 2015, the heat demand has been around 60 MWh, rising to around 70 MWh in the rest of this period. The rejected heat to the ambient accounts for 60 MWh in August, around 50 MWh in September and around 30 MWh in the rest of this period. The cooling capacity accounts to around 85 MWh in August and September, decreasing to around 75-80 MWh in the rest of *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.2 on page 53.

In the hot water circuit, the major heat fraction has been used for air heating. In August and September, the heat demand for the dehumidifier exceeded the demand of the radiators. In the rest of this period, the second highest demand accounts to the radiators.

Figure 4.1: Electric energies in the facility.

E_{dehum} (Dehumidifier), $E_{geo,heating pumps}$ (Geothermal- and heating pumps), $E_{dc fan}$ (Dry cooler fan), E_{comp} (Compressors).

Figure 4.2: Energies in the CO₂ cycle from October 2014 to March 2015 (*Period 1*) and July 2015 to September 2015 (*Period 2*).
 Q_{hw} (Rejected heat into the hot water circuit), Q_{dc} (Rejected heat by the dry cooler), Q_{geo} (Absorbed heat by the geothermal storage), Q_0 (Rejected cold to the rink floor).

Figure 4.3: Energies in the hot water circuit.

4.2 Basic power data of the cooling unit

October 2014 - March 2015 (Period 1)

In *Period 1*, weekly median values of the rejected heat by the gas cooler range between around 30 kW to around 160 kW. After week 48 in November 2014, the system has been running with the mentioned adaptations¹. Since then, median values for the rejected heat in the gas cooler have been around 165 kW. Peak values can be seen around 250–300 kW, while the lowest values range around 60–70 kW. Comparing the rejected heat in the gas cooler and the ambient temperature, it appears that the influence of this parameter is not particularly visible in this illustration.

As cooling capacity and rejected heat by the gas cooler are both linked to each other, the cooling capacity exhibits the same patterns as the rejected heat by the gas cooler. However, weekly median values for the cooling capacity range between 90 to 140 kW. After week 48 in 2014, median values for the cooling capacity have been around 130 kW. Peak values reach more than 300 kW, while the lowest values can be seen around 50 kW. Cp. figure 4.4 on page 57.

The distribution of values reveals a split into a state of lower load and state of higher load. Resulting from the usage patterns, the system is running at lower load at night time. Since the adaptations at the beginning of *Period 1* have been carried out, the system has been running considerably more stable, visible comparing the distribution of values from week 48 on. As there has been a longer period in week 13 of March 2015 without valid measurement values, this week is neglected.

Since week 48 in 2014, the rejected heat to the hot water circuit has been around 100-125 kW. After week 48, the median rejected heat by the dry cooler stabilizes around 20-25 kW. From the beginning of the season to week 51 in 2014, the dry cooler has been running for more than 75% of the time. From week 52 on however, the dry cooler has been shut off for more than 25% of the time.

While the median absorbed heat in the geothermal storage circuit has been around 10 kW in October 2014, it dropped from week 45 on. At the same time, the 75% quantile remained above 15 kW for most of the weeks. This implies that the geothermal storage has been used since then with the same variation in load, while the rejected heat quantities have been lower since week 45. Cp. figure 4.6 on page 59.

For low ambient temperatures in week 52, the rejected heat by the dry cooler is lower, ranging from 0–35 kW. While the amount of peak values in rejected heat of the dry cooler decreased, the median rejected heat remained on the same level as for different weeks and ambient temperatures. For the hot water circuit circuit, no response to this low ambient temperature is visible in this illustration.

August 2015 - December 2015 (Period 2)

The system has been started up in *Period 2* in July and has been running continuously from the fourth week of July on (relates to week 30 of 2015). In *Period 2*, weekly median values of the rejected heat in the gas cooler range are around 175 kW in August and September and around 100–125 kW in the rest of this period. Peak values in load have been around 350 kW. The median rejected cold has been around 200 kW in July, around 125 kW August and September and around 70–100 kW in the rest of this period. Cp. figure 4.5 on page 58.

From the distribution of values it appears that the base load of the cooling unit has been higher in August and September. Also, the variation in load has been lower in these two months. From week 41 on, two clusters for higher- and lower load in the system can be observed.

¹Cp. section 2.1.2 on page 18.

Median values of the rejected heat to the hot water circuit have generally increased from the beginning of the period to the beginning of September, where they stabilized around 90–100 kW. Peak values remained roughly constant. In the last two weeks of December 2015, the variation in load in the hot water circuit has been higher than in the previous weeks.

At the same time, the rejected heat to the ambient by the dry cooler has decreased, starting from median values around 80 kW to median values below 30 kW in the rest of this period. Peak values of this heat load remained roughly constant. Cp. figure 4.7 on page 60.

Distribution of calculated load per hour of the day

Median loads of the rejected heat to the hot water circuit have been around 100kW from midnight till 8 am, increasing up to 130kW in the afternoon hours. The variation in load of this heat increases at daytime.

The rejected heat by the dry cooler shows median values of around 15kW at night time, increasing to median values of around 25kW from 10–4pm. From 5pm on the median load increases to around 60kW until 10pm, when the load decreases once more.

The rejected heat to the geothermal storage shows median loads around 0–3kW throughout the night and day, decreasing after 5pm to around 0kW. The variability of the data shows a similar level from night to day times until 5pm, from then on peaks occur less often.

The cooling demand shows median values of around 100kW at night times, increasing to 110kW at 10am and increasing further up to the daily peak in this load around 9pm with a median value of 150kW. The variability is higher regarding the 25%– and 75% quantile at night time from 0–9am. Peak values however occur more often at day time. Cp. figure 4.8 on page 61.

Figure 4.4: Weekly main heat and cold quantities in *Period I*. From week 49 in 2014 on, the unit has been controlled in a more stable manner. Week 13 in 2015 has been excluded from this illustration due to missing data.
 \dot{Q}_1 (Rejected heat by the gas cooler), \dot{Q}_0 (Rejected cold to the rink floor), ϑ_{amb} (Ambient temperature).
 (Data: 1% quantile to 99% quantile).

Figure 4.5: Weekly main heat and cold quantities in *Period 2*.

\dot{Q}_1 (Rejected heat by the gas cooler), \dot{Q}_0 (Rejected cold to the rink floor), ϑ_{amb} (Ambient temperature).

(Data: 1% quantile to 99% quantile).

Figure 4.6: Weekly heat quantities in the gas cooler in *Period 1*.

$\dot{Q}_{hw, rejected}$ (Rejected heat to the hot water circuit), $\dot{Q}_{dc, rejected}$ (Rejected heat by the dry cooler), $\dot{Q}_{geo, absorbed}$ (Absorbed heat in the geothermal storage cycle).
 (Data: 1% quantile to 99% quantile).

Figure 4.7: Weekly heat quantities in the gas cooler in *Period 2*.

$\dot{Q}_{hw, rejected}$ (Rejected heat to the hot water circuit), $\dot{Q}_{dc, rejected}$ (Rejected heat by the dry cooler).

(Data: 1% quantile to 99% quantile).

Figure 4.8: Hourly variation in load in the gas cooler in *Period 1*.

4.3 Indoor– and ambient air conditions

Ambient conditions in *Period 1* can be described as autumn and winter conditions, with temperatures ranging from -16°C to 15°C . While there are weeks in whose the temperature varied only to small extent, in some weeks temperature changes of 15°C and more can be observed. The median ambient temperature of this period is around 0°C .

In contrast, *Period 2* covers the range of summer to winter conditions, with temperatures ranging from -10°C at the end of the period to around up to 25°C in the first weeks of the latter. The variation of temperature in *Period 2* has been higher in comparison. Median temperatures of this period around 9°C can be observed. Cp. figure 4.9 and shown violinplots with ambient temperatures on the previous pages².

Figure 4.9: Distribution of ambient– and indoor temperatures.

The absolute ambient humidity covers a range of about 1–6.5 grams of water per kilogram of dry air in *Period 1* and a range of around 1.2–14 grams of water per kilogram of dry air in *Period 2*. Median values of ambient humidity have been around $3.2 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/\text{kg}_{\text{air,d}}$ in *Period 1* and around $6 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/\text{kg}_{\text{air,d}}$ in *Period 2*. The indoor humidity can be observed in a range of $2.5\text{--}4.5 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/\text{kg}_{\text{air,d}}$ in *Period 1* and between $2.5\text{--}6 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/\text{kg}_{\text{air,d}}$ in *Period 2*. Median values of indoor humidity are similar in both periods. Cp. figure 4.10 on the facing page.

Despite that the ambient humidity covered significantly higher air humidities in *Period 2*, the indoor humidity has been stabilized around 4 grams of water per kilogram of dry air in *Period 2*.

The relative ambient humidity in both periods can be observed in a similar range for both periods. For 50% of the time, a relative humidity can be observed between 80– $\approx 90\%$ in *Period 1* and values in the range from 75– $\approx 90\%$ in *Period 2*. Median values are around 87% in both periods. The relative indoor humidity ranged between 54–60% with similar median values of 57% in both periods. Cp. figure 4.11 on the next page.

Indoor conditions correlate to ambient conditions. In *Period 1*, the influence of ambient temper-

²Cp. also figure ?? on page ??.

Figure 4.10: Distribution of absolute ambient– and indoor humidities.

Figure 4.11: Distribution of relative ambient– and indoor humidities.

ature on the indoor temperature is smaller compared to *Period 2*. In *Period 1*, the indoor temperature remains on a similar level for a temperature range of -10 – 5°C . In *Period 2*, the indoor temperature is roughly 5°C higher than the ambient temperature over the observed ambient temperature range. Considering the fluctuations of indoor temperature, these are higher in *Period 2*. As mentioned previously, the absolute humidities have been observed in a wider range in *Period 2*, considering indoor– as well as ambient conditions. For equal absolute ambient humidities, the indoor humidity is higher in *Period 1*. Fluctuations of absolute indoor humidity are about the same in both periods. For *Period 2*, a range of ambient humidities can be observed, where indoor humidities increased only slightly. For higher ambient humidities above $8 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}/\text{kg}_{\text{air,d}}$ however, the indoor humidity is increasing with a higher inclination. Cp. figure 4.12 on the facing page.

These differences between the two periods are considered to be to a part the result of the different methods of operation in the respective period³. As the dehumidifier has been used regularly in *Period 2*, the absolute indoor humidity is expected to be lower for the same range of absolute ambient conditions, assuming equal loads, usage patterns and ventilation rates. The indoor humidity, as well as the indoor temperature, influence the cooling demand of the ice sheet. Furthermore, these parameters are important to ensure a satisfying indoor climate, as well as to protect the facility from harms due to mould formations.

³In *Period 1*, the dehumidifier has not been used except for March 2015. In *Period 2* however, the dehumidifier has been in operation.

Figure 4.12: Correlation between indoor- and outdoor temperature and humidity. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

4.4 General system performance

The median global COP⁴ is higher in *Period 1*, same applies to the median values of the calculated COP of the upper- and lower pressure level. Regarding the global COP, a median around 5.4 can be observed in *Period 1* in contrast to around 5.0 in *Period 2*.

The median heating COP has been around 3.3 in *Period 1*, compared to around 3.3 in *Period 2*. The median cooling COP has been around 2.8 in *Period 1* in contrast to around 2.5 in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13: Distribution of coefficients of performance in both periods.
COP₁ (Heating COP), COP₀ (Cooling COP).

The system performance has been more stable in *Period 1*. The influence of ambient conditions on the system performance in *Period 2* is visible comparing it to the distribution of ambient temperature measurement values. As the median ambient temperature decreases below 5°C in week 41 of *Period 2*, the median global COP increases to around 5. Cp. figure 4.14 on the next page.

⁴Cp. section 3.1.5 on page 28 about the calculations of the coefficients of performance.

Figure 4.14: Weekly global COP data distribution.

4.5 System behaviour

4.5.1 Influence of ambient conditions

The ambient temperature is one of the drivers of system performance, as several parameters depend on it.

The influence of ambient temperature on the system behaviour becomes visible by correlating the compressor power demand to the ambient temperature. In *Period 1*, the median compressor power demand is slightly decreasing over an ambient temperature range from around -10°C to around 0°C . Over the whole temperature spectrum in this period, the median compressor power demand has been around 45kW.

In *Period 2*, the compressor power demand has been constant from below -5°C to 5°C . With a further increase of ambient temperature, the compressor power demand increased intensely. At 10°C , a compressor power demand of 45kW can be observed. From around 12°C , a compressor power demand of around 55kW can be seen.

The volatility of compressor power is significantly higher in *Period 2* over the whole observed temperature spectrum. For the same ambient temperature range, the compressor power demand has been around 10kW lower in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.15 on the facing page.

A correlation between ambient temperature and rejected heat in the gas cooler and rejected cold in the evaporator exhibits a rather constant behaviour over the observed temperature range in *Period 1*. For an increase of ambient temperature in *Period 2*, both heat quantities increase as well. Both heat quantities are significantly lower in *Period 2* compared to *Period 1* for the same ambient temperature range. Around 0°C , the median rejected heat in the gas cooler has been 50kW lower in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.16 on the next page.

Since these heat quantities are linked to the compressor power demand, it is to be expected that the increasing compressor power demand for increasing ambient temperatures is reflected in this correlation. As previously shown, the indoor temperature exhibited a stronger link to the ambient temperature in *Period 2*⁵. The indoor temperature followed the ambient temperature to some extent in this second period. This is considered to be one major reason for the visible trend of the cooling capacity in *Period 2*. In *Period 1*, when the indoor temperature is kept mostly on a set-point of around 7.5°C , no clear correlation between ambient temperature and cooling capacity can be observed.

The lower the ambient temperature, the higher the heat demand in the facility. While this is true for *Period 1*, in *Period 2*, the median rejected heat to the hot water circuit is constant for a temperature range from -5 to around 14°C . Above this temperature, a decrease with a similar gradient as in the first period can be observed for this second period.

Excess heat on the warm side of the unit can be rejected to the ambient and/or to the geothermal storage. The higher the ambient temperature, the greater is the cooling demand, while the heat demand decreases. Hence, for higher ambient temperatures, more heat has to be rejected to the ambient or to the geothermal storage on the warm side of the unit. For temperatures below 0°C , a median heat of around 20kW in *Period 1* and a median heat around 10kW has been rejected to the ambient by the dry cooler. The distribution of median values of this heat comparing the two periods overlap for a temperature range from around 0°C to around 6°C .

Median values of the rejected heat to the geothermal storage circuit are zero over the whole ambient temperature spectrum in *Period 1*. Hence, this heat quantity has been zero for at least 50% of the time. However, the 90% quantile values can be observed in the range of 20–25kW with a

⁵Cp. figure ?? on page ??.

Figure 4.15: Correlation between power consumption of the compressors and the ambient temperature.
(Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Figure 4.16: Correlation between heat- and cold in the unit and the ambient temperature.
(Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

constant behaviour over the observed temperature range. Cp. figure 4.17.

The lower heat demand corresponding to a lower rejected heat to the hot water circuit in *Period 2* reflects the lower indoor temperature in this period for the illustrated temperature range⁶. The heat demand exhibits an influence by the ambient temperature in *Period 1*, as it is linearly decreasing for increasing ambient temperatures.

Figure 4.17: Correlation of heat quantities in the gas cooler and the ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

By tendency, the heat recovery ratio decreases with an increase of ambient temperature. Considering the heat recovery ratio in *Period 1*, it decreased from 120% to 100% from -5 to around 5°C. In *Period 2*, a decrease from 110% to around 100% can be observed from around 0–10°C. From 10–20°C, a linear decrease with a higher inclination can be observed from around 100% to around 75%. For the same temperature range, the heat recovery ratio has been higher by tendency in *Period 1*. Cp. figure 4.18 on the next page.

Illustrated values for low temperatures show a unsteady trend, resulting from a low amount of available data for these temperatures. Hence, these values have a low significance.

For the shared ambient temperature range, the gas cooler exit temperature has been 5–10°C lower in *Period 1*. The variation of ϑ_3 is higher in the first period, varying between 12–35°C constantly over the covered ambient temperature range.

This variation is in the range of 12–30°C in the *Period 2*. From 10°C on, 10% quantile values have been linearly increasing for increasing ambient temperature values. For this linear increase, the 10% quantile values are constantly 2°C higher than the ambient temperature, indicating a high efficiency for the gas cooler for these cases. Cp. figure 4.19 on the facing page.

As can be observed from this illustration, a lower gas cooler exit temperature would have been possible for ambient temperatures below 10°C. However, the system control stabilized ϑ_3 at a higher temperature level in both periods. This indicates that the required enthalpy spread over the evaporator is provided with the illustrated gas cooler exit temperatures. This supposition fits to the previously observed higher cooling demand in *Period 1* in comparison, as the gas cooler exit temperature is lower in comparison in this period.

⁶Cp. also section 4.3 on page 62 about indoor- and ambient air conditions.

Figure 4.18: Correlation between heat recovery ratio and the ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Figure 4.19: Correlation between gas cooler exit temperature and the ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

The median system performance for the heating– and cooling coefficient of performance in *Period 1* is higher than in *Period 2* for the shared ambient temperature range. In *Period 1*, the system performance is about constant with an increase in ambient temperature. In *Period 2*, the system performance increases from -5 to 2°C, while from around 2 to above 12°C, the COP decrease until around 15°C. For higher temperatures, an increase with ambient temperature can be observed once more. Cp. figure 4.20.

Figure 4.20: Correlation between COP_1 and COP_0 and the ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

The median global COP can be observed around 5.5 for the whole temperature spectrum of *Period 1*. Within the same temperature spectrum, the global COP of both periods are on a similar level. In *Period 2*, the median global COP decreases slightly over a temperature range of around -5 to around 5°C. For ambient temperature from 5– around 15°C and above, a strong decrease from around 5.0 to around 3.6 can be observed. Cp. figure 4.21 on the facing page.

Comparing the measured– and calculated median optimal discharge pressure for different ambient temperatures in *Period 1*, only a small deviation in the range of 1–3bar can be observed over the covered ambient temperature range. For ambient temperatures below 0°C in *Period 1*, the discharge pressure has been too high by tendency, while it has been too low by tendency for temperatures in the range of about 2–6°C. For ambient temperatures below 0°C, the median discharge pressure settled at around 89bar. The calculated optimal discharge pressure ranged from around 75bar up to more than 90 bar.

In *Period 2*, a similar tendency can be observed. However, the median discharge pressure settled around 89–90bar for a temperature range from below -5°C to around 8°C. The deviation from the optimal calculated discharge pressure is higher in *Period 2* in comparison. Also, the pressure range for the calculated optimal discharge pressure is higher in *Period 2*, ranging from 70bar up to above 120bar. Cp. figure 4.22 on page 74.

As can be derived from this illustration, the discharge pressure has been too high for ambient temperatures below 5–8°C, in case a control opting for a maximization of the COP is the aim. The opposite is true for ambient temperatures above these values, where the discharge pressure should be increased.

Figure 4.21: Correlation between COP_{global} and the ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%-90% quantile).

Figure 4.22: Correlation between real- and optimal discharge pressure for a maximized COP and the ambient temperature.
(Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

4.5.2 Influence of indoor conditions

Regarding the influence of indoor temperature on the heat- and cold demand in the facility, the cooling capacity shows a distinctive response to a change in indoor air temperature. A linear increase can be observed for increasing indoor temperatures. This trend is especially clear visible in *Period 2*, as in this period, the range of indoor air temperatures has been higher. For indoor temperatures around 5°C, the median cooling demand has been 80kW in this period. At an indoor temperature of 10°C, the median cooling demand reaches 120kW. For the heat demand, a clear trend is not distinguishable. Cp. figure 4.23.

Figure 4.23: Correlation between cooling capacity, heat demand and the indoor air temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

4.5.3 Load dependencies

The system performance depends on the gas cooler exit temperature ϑ_3 . In case all other system parameters are maintained constant, the system performance increases with a decrease of this temperature. This is due that the available enthalpy difference in the gas cooler and the evaporator increases, when the gas cooler exit temperature is lowered.

In both periods, the COP_1 and COP_0 show a linear behaviour, increasing with a decrease of ϑ_3 . For both periods and for the same gas cooler exit temperature, a similar median COP can be observed. However, median COP are slightly higher in *Period 2*. The variability has been rather constant over the observed temperatures, however it is higher in the second period. In this second period, the spread between high- and low COP is around 0.5, whereas in *Period 1*, this spread is around 0.25. Cp. figure 4.25 on the next page.

Computed cooling COP of a theoretical model of a trans-critical CO_2 cycle developed by Prof. Dr. Sawalha as part of his Ph.D. thesis cover a gas cooler exit temperature curve of 32.5°C [17, p. 50]. For a discharge pressure of 80–90bar, a cooling COP of around 2.5–2.4 has been calculated in Sawalha's thesis. The calculated cooling COP in this present work ranges between around 1.9 to 2.25. This illustrates an optimization potential.

Figure 4.24: Data distribution of the gas cooler exit temperature.

Figure 4.25: Correlation between COP_1 and COP_0 and the gas cooler exit temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

The global COP increases as well for decreasing gas cooler exit temperatures. It has been distinctively more stable in *Period 1*, as the variability is significantly higher in *Period 2*. The spread between 10%– and 90% quantile is around 0.5 to 1.0 in *Period 1* and 1.5 to 2.5 in *Period 2*. A roughly quadratic decrease can be observed for this correlation, as the gradient of global COP decrease increases with rising gas cooler exit temperatures. Cp. figure 4.26.

As the global COP illustrates useful cold– and heat quantities in relation to the required input power, it exhibits that the system performance increased by tendency with a decreasing gas cooler exit temperature.

Figure 4.26: Correlation between COP_{global} and the the gas cooler exit temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

The discharge pressure increases with an increase of heat recovery ratio. For a heat recovery ratio smaller 100%, the cooling demand exceeds the heat demand and the discharge pressure decreases. In both periods, a linear median decrease of discharge pressure can be observed for decreasing heat recovery ratios below 100%. However, the gradient of this decrease is steeper in *Period 1* in comparison. Hence, for the same heat recovery ratio, the discharge pressure is higher in *Period 2*. Also, the spread in discharge pressure over the shared range of *HRR* is higher in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.27 on the next page.

The global COP correlated to the heat recovery ratio exhibits a distinguishable behaviour in *Period 1*. For heat recovery ratios from 70–120%, the global COP settled around 5.5 in *Period 1*. From a *HRR* of 130%, the global COP decreases. Three areas of heat recovery ratio can be observed, where the system settled in most cases. Those are heat recovery ratios of around 80–95%, around 115–120% and around 140–150%. The highest density of observed values can be seen at a heat recovery ratio around 140–150%, corresponding to global COP of around 5.0.

In *Period 2*, the global COP has been lower for the same observed range of heat recovery ratio. In this period, the correlation between the global COP and *HRR* is less distinguishable. Again, three clusters of highest density can be observed: For a *HRR* of 80–95%, 115–120% and around 130–140%. The highest density has been in the range of 130–140% of heat recovery ratio, corresponding to a global COP of around 5.0. Cp. figure 4.28 on page 79.

Although the median global COP by tendency is lower in the *Period 2*, for the most common heat recovery ratio, the system exhibits a similar global COP.

Figure 4.27: Correlation between discharge pressure and heat recovery ratio.
(Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Regarding a control of the system for a maximization of COP, it can be observed that the discharge pressure has been too high for heat recovery ratios higher than around 120%. Below this value, the discharge pressure has been rather low. However, the deviation from the optimal discharge pressure is rather low for a heat recovery ratio of 90–120%. In *Period 1*, this deviation is smaller over the whole covered range of heat recovery ratios than in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.29 on page 80. This fits to the previously shown system behaviour regarding the optimal discharge pressure. As mentioned above, for low ambient temperatures, the heat recovery ratio increases⁷. Furthermore, it has been shown that the discharge pressure has been rather too high for low ambient temperatures⁸. Comparing the correlation of global COP and heat recovery ratio, as well as the correlation of optimal discharge pressure and heat recovery ratio, the global COP is the highest for small deviations of discharge pressure and optimal discharge pressure. This applies to the heat recovery ratio of around 90–120%, where it has been shown that for this range of *HRR*, the global COP has been the highest.

From a broad perspective, the discharge pressure has been more stable in *Period 1*. Mainly, the discharge pressure has been around 90 bar, partly going down to 70 bar. In the first three weeks of *Period 2*, when the system has been started up, the discharge pressure ranged between 35–60 bars for 50% of the time with peaks around 90 bar. From week 30 to week 33, the discharge pressure ranged between below 60 bar to 90 bars, with a median between 70–80 bars. In the rest of this period, the discharge pressure has been mostly above around 88 bar. In the weeks 48–50, the discharge pressure has been locked to 90 percent for test purposes. Cp. figure 4.30 on page 81.

⁷Cp. the correlation of heat recovery ratio and ambient temperature in figure 4.18 on page 71.

⁸Cp. the correlation of discharge pressure and ambient temperature in figure 4.22 on page 74.

Figure 4.28: Correlation between COP_{global} and the heat recovery ratio.
(Marked area in the topmost plot: 10%–90% quantile. Density plot using 50 levels).

Figure 4.29: Correlation between real– and optimal discharge pressure for a maximized COP and the heat recovery ratio.
(Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Figure 4.30: Weekly data distribution of the discharge pressure.

4.6 Components

4.6.1 Dry cooler performance

The calculated efficiency of the dry cooler shows a distinctive difference between the two periods. The median efficiency is around 95% in *Period 1*, while in *Period 2*, the median efficiency is around 65%. Cp. figure 4.31.

It has to be noted that this calculated efficiency of the dry cooler is not a criterion for judging the efficiency of this component in terms of quality aspects, but rather for comparing the two periods. This is because to lower the gas cooler temperature level as much as possible is not always the aim of the system control. The system control adapts the gas cooler activity depending on the opted gas cooler exit temperature, whereas this temperature depends on the discharge pressure and the required cooling capacity.

Figure 4.31: Distribution of calculated dry cooler efficiency.

4.6.2 Compressors

The total efficiency data of the compressors shows a median value of around 70% for both periods. 50% of the calculated efficiency has been between around 68–73%. Cp. figure 4.32 on the facing page.

The efficiency of the compressors depend to some extent on the pressure ratio. A clustered behaviour of the pressure ratio can be observed, with the highest density in occurrence around a pressure ratio of 3.10. Cp. figure 4.33 on the next page.

Figure 4.32: Distribution of calculated total compressor efficiency.

Figure 4.33: Total efficiency of the compressors correlated to the pressure ratio.
(Marked area in the topmost plot: 10%–90% quantile. Density plot using 50 levels).

4.6.3 Dehumidification system

The dehumidifier has been intensively used in the beginning of *Period 2*. In August 2015, the median total power consumption of the dehumidifier has been around 35 kW. 25 kW of the latter were provided using electric energy. While this electric energy consumption decreased from September on to below 15 kW, the electric energy consumption has still been higher throughout the season compared to the heat power consumption. Cp. figure 4.34.

Figure 4.34: Weekly median values of the two power sources of the recovery function of the dehumidifier. Absolute humidity difference of indoor– and outdoor humidity $\Delta\text{Humidity} = \rho_{w,\text{indoor}} - \rho_{w,\text{ambient}}$

The activity of the dehumidification system can be described as a function of indoor– and ambient conditions. To some extent, this activity depends on the difference of absolute air humidity between indoor– and ambient air. Three electric power steps can be observed at around 25kW, 15kW and 0kW. The heat demand has been around 10kW over a wide range of humidity differences. Cp. figure 4.37 on page 86.

The deduced pre–heated air temperature in the dehumidifier has been in the range of around 20 to 40°C , with a median temperature around 30–35°C . For the measured post–heated air, a wider range of temperatures can be observed. This post–heated air temperature shows a median temperature of around 60°C , with a 75% quantile of over 100°C . Cp. figure 4.35 on the facing page.

As shown previously in section 4.7.1 on page 88 about the hot water circuit, the outlet temperature on the warm side of the dehumidifier heat exchanger has been between 57– and 60°C for 80% of the time. After the heat transfer of the hot water circuit to the air volume flow through the heat exchanger in the dehumidifier, the pre–heated air reaches the mentioned median temperature of 30–35°C . This relates to a calculated efficiency of around 40% for most cases. Cp. figure 4.36 on the facing page.

As can be concluded from these measures, the heat usage of the dehumidifier could be increased by increasing the inlet temperature on the warm side of the heat exchanger in the dehumidifier.

Figure 4.35: 25%, 50% and 75% quantiles of the dehumidifier recovery air.

Figure 4.36: Correlation between dehumidifier efficiency and difference between indoor- and outdoor absolute humidity. (Marked area in the topmost plot: 10%–90% quantile. Density plot using 50 levels).

Figure 4.37: Correlation between heat- and electric power demand of the dehumidifier and the difference of absolute air humidity between indoor- and ambient air. (Marked area in the topmost plot: 10%-90% quantile. Density plot using 50 levels).

This way, the pre-heated air temperature could be increased and the electric power demand could be lowered. As the discharge temperature of the main CO₂ circuit is around 90°C and higher, a direct heat exchanger after the discharge side of the compressors could serve this need. Another way of increasing the recovered heat, the dehumidifier heat exchanger could be adapted to fit the available temperature level of the hot water circuit better. Thereby, the efficiency of the heat exchanger providing the thermal connection to the hot water circuit could be increased.

4.7 Subsystems

4.7.1 Hot water circuit

The heat demand that accounts for the post-heating of hot water is below 5 kW for most of the time, yet upper peaks reach more than 20 kW. As to be expected, the distribution of values of this heat demand includes zero values. This description applies to both periods.

Dehumidification accounts to a heat demand in the range 0–10 kW, at which a major share of values can be seen either at 0 or at around 10 kW, indicating a stepwise behaviour.

The heat demand of the radiators ranges between 10–20 kW for most of the time in *Period 1*. However in *Period 2*, it ranged mostly between 8–15 kW.

In both periods, the heat demand for the post-heating for the purpose of re-surfacings is close to zero for most of the time. However, peaks of this load reach up to 50–60 kW and more. For a short time, this heat demand reaches the range of demand for the biggest share in this circuit, which is air heating.

Air heating also accounts for the highest peaks in load, with a demand up to 120 kW and more. The median can be seen at 80 kW in *Period 1*, while in *Period 2*, it has been around 65 kW. The range of values of this demand is high, from 40–125 kW in *Period 1* and 10–115 kW in *Period 2*. Pre-heating of cold water shows a similar distribution of values as for re-surfacing. It ranges between 0–5 kW for most of the time, while peaks reach up to 40 kW in *Period 1* and more than 60 kW in *Period 2*.

The heat demand for freeze protection ranges between 0–10 kW in *Period 1* and 0–20 kW in *Period 2*. The 25% quantile can be seen close to 0kW, while a major part of this heat is in the range of 5–10 kW. Cp. figure 4.38 on the next page.

For the sake of readability of figure 4.39 on page 91, the highest- and lowest 1% of the data have been removed, to enable a better analysis of the broader range of data. Hence, the illustrated quantiles in this figure represent the 24%- and 74% quantile of the data.

The heat demand of the post-heating for the hot water demand remains within a cluster above zero at night time for most of the time. The median heat demand increases only slightly throughout the day, whereas the volatility is increasing for afternoon and evening times.

The heat demand for dehumidification shows a similar distribution for all hours of the day, with two clusters of data. Either the power demand is below 3 kW or above 7 kW. This implies a stepwise behaviour of the dehumidifier control.

Median heat loads of the radiators are steady throughout the day around 9 kW. At night times, 50% of the data is in a range between 8–13 kW, while around noon the range is between 4.5 to around 12kW. The variation of this load is high.

As mentioned above, the heat demand for re-surfacings is generally low with a strong increase in case a re-surfacing occurs. A similar distribution can be observed throughout the day.

Air heating as the highest demand in this group shows a median load around 60 kW for all hours of the day. A behaviour similar as for radiators can be observed, as the range of values between the 24% and 74% quantile is increased for hours around noon and afternoon. 50% of the data ranges between 55–65 kW for night- and early day hours from midnight to noon. The range between these quantiles is between 50–70kW for the afternoon- and evening hours.

This demand is generally on a high level without much variation at night hours, whereas the variation in load is increased at day time.

As observed before, the heat demand for pre-heating shows a similar distribution of values as the heat demand for the post-heating of re-surfacing water. However, peaks of this load are 50 kW and more.

Figure 4.38: Distribution of heat quantities in the hot water circuit.

Freeze protection as one of the lowest demands in this group beside dehumidification shows a median load of around 4.5 kW for all hours of the day. 24% of the values are zero, while 74% of the calculated heat is below 9 kW. Peaks can be seen up to 18 kW and more. Cp. figure 4.39 on the next page.

In figure 4.40 on page 92, the temperatures in the hot water circuit are illustrated. The volatility of the corresponding heat fluxes are visible comparing the 90%- and 10% quantile. Due to that each volatility of the temperature at one position influences the volatility at the next position, the volatility generally increases. The highest demand for heat accounts to air heating, therefore the temperature loss between sensors VP1_{GT5} and VP1_{GT6} is the highest in comparison. Comparing the two periods, it can be seen that in *Period 2*, the volatility is higher than in *Period 1*. Also, the dehumidifier has been working in *Period 2*, while it has not been used in *Period 1*.

The rejected heat to the hot water circuit in correlation to the ambient temperature shows a linear decline for the median values in the illustrated sectors in *Period 1*.

However, in *Period 2* these median values have been constant over the same temperature range and beyond. For ambient temperatures above around 12–14°C, the heat demand declines.

The variability of the two periods looks generally similar, whereas the 90% quantile decreases below ambient temperatures of around 0–3°C. Cp. figure 4.41 on page 93.

The heat demand of the radiators shows a linear behaviour. The variation between high- and low values is reasonably constant over the whole temperature range. In *Period 2*, the heat demand for radiators is smaller, while the variation is slightly higher. Cp. figure 4.42 on page 93.

The heat demand for air heating shows a linear behaviour in *Period 1*, decreasing with an increase of ambient temperature.

In *Period 2* however, a fixed median heat demand of around 70 kW is reached below ambient temperatures of around 5°C. Above this temperature, the heat demand decreases with smaller declination between 5– around 14°C and higher declination above this temperature. Cp. figure 4.43 on page 94.

Efficiency of the heat exchanger *HX1*

The calculated efficiency of the heat exchanger *HX1*⁹ varies between 88% and 92% for 50% of the time in *Period 1*. In *Period 2*, the calculated efficiency is in the range of 91% up to 97%. Cp. figure 4.44 on page 94.

The correlation between calculated efficiency and the ratio of heat capacity rates R_1 illustrates the behaviour over the covered spectrum of operational states.

The median efficiency of this heat exchanger is above 85% over a spectrum of $0.1 \leq R_1 \leq 0.55$, with a peak in efficiency around $R_1 = 0.25$. The most common operational state is around $R_1 = 0.33$, with an efficiency close to 90%. Cp. figure 4.45 on page 95.

The heat exchanger has got a steady behaviour regarding the efficiency over the covered spectrum of operational states. Also, it illustrates that the optimization potential concerning a shift in operational conditions is low.

⁹The heat exchanger 1 connects the CO₂ circuit and the hot water circuit.

Figure 4.39: Distribution of heat quantities in the hot water circuit for different hours of the day. The highest- and lowest 1% of the data are removed in order to show the broader range of data better. Shown quantiles: 24%, 50% and 74% quantile.
Data: *Period 2*

Figure 4.40: Temperature trends in the hot water circuit and corresponding heat flows.

Figure 4.41: Correlation between rejected heat to the hot water circuit and ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Figure 4.42: Correlation between heat demand of the radiators and the ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Figure 4.43: Correlation between heat demand for air heating and ambient temperature. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Figure 4.44: Distribution of calculated heat exchanger 1 (HX1) efficiencies.

Figure 4.45: Correlation between *HX1* efficiency and the ratio of heat capacity rates.
 (Marked area in the topmost plot: 10%–90% quantile. Density plot using 50 levels).

Hot water circuit heat potential

As previously mentioned, the heat demand in this circuit varies. As a result, the lower temperature level of the hot water circuit varies as well. In both observed periods, peaks in this lower temperature around 20°C can be observed. The median lower temperature in the hot water circuit is around 25 to around 30°C in both periods¹⁰. Hence, additional heat loads have to have a lower temperature than this lower temperature level. As described in section 3.2.2 on page 44, two different scenarios are covered in order to evaluate the hot water circuit heat potential.

Scenario 1

For a step-wise decreased lower temperature level $\vartheta_{HX1,in(c)}$ in the hot water circuit, the median additional heat available increases linearly to around 40kW for *Period 1*–data and 50kW for *Period 2*–data for $\vartheta_{HX1,in(c)} = 15^{\circ}\text{C}$. The calculated heat potential for this scenario is higher in *Period 2*. 50% of the calculated heat potential is around 30–50kW in *Period 1* for the lower temperature level $\vartheta_{HX1,in(c)}$ of 15°C, in contrast to 40 to more than 100kW in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.46 on the following page and figure 4.47 on the next page.

Scenario 2

For a step-wise decreased lower temperature level $\vartheta_{HX1,in(c)}$ and an increased water volume flow in the hot water circuit, the median additional heat available increases linearly to around 100kW for *Period 1*–data and 140kW for *Period 2*–data for $\vartheta_{HX1,in(c)}$ of 15°C. 50% of the calculated heat potential is around 90–105kW in *Period 1* for the lower temperature level $\vartheta_{HX1,in(c)}$ of 15°C, in contrast to 100 to around 190kW in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.48 on page 97 and figure 4.49 on page 97.

¹⁰Cp. figure 4.40 on page 92 about the temperature distribution in the hot water circuit.

Figure 4.46: Scenario 1: The volume flow is assumed to equal the reference scenario while the lower temperature level of the hot water circuit is lowered step-wise from 30–7.5°C . (Data: *Period 1*)

Figure 4.47: Scenario 1: The volume flow is assumed to equal the reference scenario while the lower temperature level of the hot water circuit is lowered step-wise from 30–7.5°C . (Data: *Period 2*)

Figure 4.48: Scenario 2: The volume flow is assumed to be maintained on a high level while the lower temperature level of the hot water circuit is lowered step-wise from 30–7.5°C . (Data: *Period 1*)

Figure 4.49: Scenario 2: The volume flow is assumed to be maintained on a high level while the lower temperature level of the hot water circuit is lowered step-wise from 30–7.5°C . (Data: *Period 2*)

4.7.2 Geothermal storage

The geothermal return temperature depends on the activity in the geothermal storage circuit and hence is influenced by the amount– and temperature of heat quantities stored. Since every measurement involves inaccuracies, rather than using the minimum, the lowest 5% quantile of the geothermal storage return temperature is used.

Over *Period 1*, the absorbed geothermal storage heat quantity decreased by tendency. Starting at a mean over one week around 10kW, it decreased to an amount of around 6kW in the last two months of the period. A drop in absorbed heat can be observed at mid of November 2014, linked to an increase of the 5% quantile of the geothermal storage return temperature. This results from a period from the 14th to the 17th of November 2014, where the geothermal storage has not been used. The behaviour of the return temperature is rather constant for some periods and volatile for others. Cp figure 4.50.

As can be derived from this illustration, the geothermal return temperature varies. Yet, the general trend is a slight increase of around 1°C over *Period 1*, when only a return temperature level higher 9°C and smaller 12°C is considered. This trend represents only the trend of this temperature level. The lowest return temperature is around 6°C .

Figure 4.50: Rolling 5% quantile of the return temperature ϑ_{TT19} , mean absorbed heat quantity and pump signal of the geothermal storage with a window of one week. Regression over $9 \leq \vartheta_{geo,return} \leq 12$

Heat is rejected to the geothermal storage with an intermittent behaviour with several cycles over one day. At the beginning of one cycle, typically the temperature difference between in– and outlet temperature of the geothermal storage is relatively high. Despite that the pump signal is maintained at a pump signal below 50% for most of the time, the temperature difference decreases. Cp. figure 4.51 on the next page.

Looking at a detail of a cycle of rejected heat to the geothermal storage, the previously mentioned behaviour is visible better. As a result of the decreasing temperature difference between in– and outlet of the geothermal storage for one cycle, the absorbed heat in this circuit decreases as well. A certain inertia can be observed for the sensors at the beginning of each cycle. Cp. figure 4.52 on the facing page.

Figure 4.51: Geothermal control behaviour: Geothermal inlet– and outlet temperature and pump signal over one day.

Figure 4.52: Geothermal inlet– and outlet temperature and pump signal over one cycle.

By correlating the absorbed heat in the geothermal storage to the pump signal of the latter, a parabolic trend can be observed. For low geothermal pump signals, the corresponding absorbed heat quantity is low. At a pump signal of around 50%, a peak of absorbed heat is reached. For higher pump signals, the absorbed heat is declining once more. Cp. figure 4.53.

Figure 4.53: Correlation between absorbed heat in the geothermal storage and geothermal pump signal.
(Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

A similar behaviour can be observed using a correlation of absorbed heat in the geothermal storage and the efficiency of the heat exchanger *HX2*. A peak of this heat corresponds to an efficiency of *HX2* of around 45%. Cp. figure 4.54 on the facing page.

Efficiency of the heat exchanger *HX2*

The calculated efficiency of the heat exchanger *HX2* is spread over a broad spectrum of values. The median efficiency is around 50%. 50% of the time this heat exchanger is operated at an efficiency in the range of 40–60%. Lower peak values can be observed below 20%, upper peaks of more than 90%. Cp. figure 4.55 on the next page.

As this efficiency is calculated using the dry cooler bypass valve, as well as the geothermal storage pump as criteria, it is to be expected that this leads to wide range of calculated efficiencies. This is due to the inertia of temperature sensors, while this inertia is not excluded in this data.

The correlation between calculated efficiency and the ratio of heat capacity rates R_1 illustrates that by tendency, the efficiency is rising with an increase of this ratio. The state with the highest density in occurrence is around $R_1 = 0.85$. Cp. figure 4.56 on page 102.

The results of this heat exchanger show that the optimization potential regarding a shift in operational conditions is high.

Figure 4.54: Correlation between absorbed heat in the geothermal storage and efficiency of the geothermal storage heat exchanger *HX2*. (Marked area: 10%–90% quantile).

Figure 4.55: Efficiency of the heat exchanger 2

Figure 4.56: Correlation between efficiency of the heat exchanger 2 and the ratio of heat capacity rates.
(Marked area in the topmost plot: 10%–90% quantile. Density plot using 50 levels).

4.7.3 Electricity systems

The electric power demand for the compressors accounts for around 85% of the total electric power demand measured by the installed sensors in the facility in *Period 1*¹¹. In *Period 2*, the compressors account for a power demand of around 70%. In *Period 2*, the dehumidifier has been used and this demand accounts to almost 20% of the overall electric power demand in this period. Rink pump, dry cooler fans and geothermal storage– and heating pumps contribute to the overall electric power demand in the range of up to 4kW. Cp. figure 4.57 on the facing page.

Comparing monthly electric community data and the measured power demand of the facility, a difference of around 10–15MWh can be observed. This demand gap is not covered by the facilities power demand monitoring system. Cp. figure 4.58 on page 104.

¹¹Cp. section 3.4 on page 48 about the methodology regarding electric systems in the facility.

Figure 4.57: Compressor power and auxiliary power consumers in the facility.

Figure 4.58: Comparison of measured energy demand in the facility and measured demand by the community.

Figure 4.59: Derived electric energy demand share using the measured demand in the facility and provided by the community.

Due to that the compressor power range is so much higher than for the other consumers in this group, a separate plot for the compressors and the remaining power demands are shown below. Same applies to the rink pump, as this power demand range is low, compared to the other electricity consumers.

For the compressor power demand, a clustered distribution can be observed. A median compressor power demand of around 45kW in both periods can be seen. In both periods, the distribution of data is similar regarding the observed clusters. In *Period 1* however, the compressor power demand ranges between 20–75kW for the observed 98% of the data, while in *Period 2*, a range between 18 to around 115kW can be observed. The mentioned clusters illustrate the step-wise power increase of the non-frequency controlled compressors. Cp. figure 4.60.

Figure 4.60: Distribution of compressor power demand. The highest- and lowest 1% of the data are removed in order to show the broader range of data better.

The rink pump, shows a clustered distribution of measured power demand, with a median at 0.5kW in *Period 1* and a median around 0.7kW in *Period 2*. In *Period 2*, the rink pump has almost shown only this power demand throughout this period.

The dry cooler fan show a power demand in the range of 0–0.5 kW, with peaks up to 4kW. In *Period 2*, this power demand can be observed higher in comparison, whereas also peaks close to 4kW occurred more often.

The geothermal storage and heating pumps show a clustered distribution in a range of around 1.4 to about 2.0kW in *Period 1* and from around 1.3 to 2.6kW in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 4.61 on the next page.

The lighting demand can be observed in a range between 0–15kW, with a median in both periods at 5kW. Differences between the two periods regarding this consumer are small.

The dehumidifier shows a step-wise behaviour within a range between 0–26kW. A median around 3kW and a 75% quantile can be observed at around 15kW. Hence, 75% of the time in this period this power demand has been below 15kW. As shown before, the dehumidifier has been used more intensely in the warm months of this period, hence the observed peak values account to these months. Cp. figure 4.62 on page 107.

The distribution of compressor power demand for every hour of the day shows a similar distribution as the previously shown pattern of the hot water circuit¹² with peaks in load at 4,7 and 9pm. Cp. figure 4.63 on page 108.

¹²Cp. figure 4.8 on page 61.

Figure 4.61: Distribution of electric power demand of rink pump, dry cooler fans and heating pumps. The highest- and lowest 1% of the data are removed in order to show the broader range of data better.

Figure 4.62: Overview over electric power demand of lighting and dehumidification. The highest- and lowest 1% of the data are removed in order to show the broader range of data better.

This is expected to be the result of the heat recovery control mode, as the system controlled by the heat demand most often.

The rink pump power demand distribution shows median values of 0.5kW from midnight to 3pm. Between 4 and 6pm, median values incline to 0.55kW, and from 7 to 9pm values incline to 0.6kW. This underlines the increased load on the system in later afternoon and evening hours.

The dry cooler fan power consume distribution for different hours of the day looks similar throughout the day, while peaks in load occur more often in the afternoon- and evening hours.

Likewise, geothermal storage pump and heating pumps show a continuous distribution pattern throughout the hours of the day.

Lighting power demand shows a median load of close to zero for hours from 1–5pm. For day time hours, the median can be observed around 7–7.5kW. From 10pm to midnight, this load shows median values of around 2kW. Cp. figure 4.63 on the next page.

Figure 4.63: Distribution of electric power demand for different hours of the day.
Data: *Period 1*

5 Specific system analysis

5.1 Heat demand for additional heated space

As has been described in section 1.5.2 on page 5, presumably added heated spaces will lead to a higher heat demand in the future. Given that the already existing heated areas correspond to the same room height, the heat demand for these added heated spaces can be estimated. Based on the heat demand for radiators of *Period 1* and *Period 2*, the estimated additional heat demand is below 0.5 kW for most of the time, cp. figure 5.1.

Figure 5.1: Predicted heat demand for additional heated spaces.

5.2 Monitoring system COP calculation

The calculated global COP of the Green & Cool system differs from a scientifically correct value¹. The calculated global COP has a median of around 5.4, whereas the Green&Cool shows a median of around 4.0. Cp. figure 5.2 on the next page.

5.3 System performance with an internal heat exchanger

The system performance using an internal heat exchanger² can be increased by an increase in transferred heat from the end of the gas cooler to the suction line of the compressors. In the

¹The global COP is calculated using equation (3.19) on page 29.

²Cp. section 3.1.9 on page 31 about the methodology of this internal heat exchanger evaluation.

Figure 5.2: Green & Cool COP compared to the scientifically correct value.
(Data: *Period 1*)

following, the internal heat exchanger is also referred to as *IHX*.

Assuming an efficiency of 50% for the *IHX*, the calculated global COP of both the *IHX*- and the reference scenario are about the same. The deviation in COP increase from the reference scenario at an inner heat exchanger efficiency of 0% illustrates the inaccuracy of this model. Cp. figure 5.3 on the next page.

While the system performance can be increased this way, the available heat for heat recovery purposes decreases, cp. figure 5.4 on page 112.

To meet the load profile of the heat recovery system of the reference scenario, the outlet temperature of the heat recovery heat exchanger *HXI* has to be lowered. By lowering this outlet temperature in a range of around 1-10%, the rejected heat to the hot water circuit can be stabilized to cover the measured demand.

By calculating the difference of measured heat demand in the hot water circuit and available heat depending on different inner heat exchanger efficiencies, the gap between demand and supply becomes visible, cp. figure 5.5 on page 113.

As it has been shown before, this supply–demand gap increases with an increase of the inner heat exchanger efficiency. Furthermore, the volatility of this gap increases.

Figure 5.3: Coefficients of performance, reference scenario compared with the inner heat exchanger scenario. The relative increase of COP_0 is higher than the relative increase COP_1 . The deviation in COP increase from the reference scenario at an inner heat exchanger efficiency of 0% illustrates the inaccuracy of this model.

Figure 5.4: Available heat for the heat recovery system for different inner heat exchanger efficiencies. Depending on the inner heat exchanger efficiency, the outlet temperature of the heat recovery heat exchanger $HX1$ ($\vartheta_{\text{HX1,out,set}}$) has to be lowered, in order to provide the heat recovery system with the same heat as in the reference scenario. The deviation at a inner heat exchanger efficiency of 0% illustrates the inaccuracy of this model.

Figure 5.5: Difference of heat demand and available heat for different inner heat exchanger efficiencies.

5.4 Rink floor

5.4.1 Ice temperature control

In *Period 1*, the ice temperature is controlled using an embedded sensor in the ice sheet, while in *Period 2*, the ice temperature is controlled using an infra-red sensor pointing on the ice surface³. Comparing the fluctuation of cooling capacity, apparently the fluctuation is higher in *Period 2*, when the ice temperature has been controlled using the infra-red sensor. Comparing the fluctuation of ice temperature measured by the embedded sensor in both periods, the fluctuation is higher in *Period 1*. Cp. figure 5.6 on the next page.

This example may illustrate that the ice temperature can be stabilized more closely on its set point using the infra-red sensor in *Period 2*. However, this leads to an increased fluctuation in cooling capacity.

The derived re-surfacing time τ_{resurf} is the time from the beginning to the end of a traced re-surfacing. This re-surfacing time is significantly reduced using the infra-red sensor. While the median re-surfacing time has been around 100 minutes in *Period 1* with the embedded sensor, a median re-surfacing time of around 40 minutes can be observed with the infra-red sensor used in *Period 2*. Cp. figure 5.7 on page 115.

As has been previously shown, the fluctuation of cooling capacity increased with the usage of the infra-red sensor. The relative cooling capacity is the calculated cooling capacity while a re-surfacing is ongoing in relation to the mean cooling capacity throughout the corresponding period. The median relative cooling capacity using the embedded sensor has been around 130%, while it has been around 160% with the infra-red sensor. The spread of this relative power is significantly higher with the usage of the infra-red sensor, with peak relative cooling capacities of more than 250% of the mean cooling capacity. Cp. figure 5.7 on page 115.

³Cp. section 2.1.2 on page 18 about the measurement periods and section 3.1.10 on page 34 about the ice temperature control. Cp. also figure ?? on page ??.

Figure 5.6: Fluctuation of cooling capacity and ice temperature compared. Hourly mean values.

Combining these two results, the cooling demand during a re-surfacing is calculated. The derived median cooling demand during a re-surfacing has been around 250kWh with the embedded sensor in *Period 1*. With the infra-red sensor in *Period 2*, this median cooling demand has been around 130kWh. The needed cooling demand throughout a re-surfacing is lower using the infra-red sensor in this comparison. Cp. figure 5.7 on the facing page.

The time needed to stabilize the ice temperature back on its set point from the maximum deviation of the latter, $\tau_{2,resurf}$, is one of the considered parameters that illustrate the performance of the control strategies. Another one is the maximum temperature deviation from the set point, throughout a re-surfacing. Both parameters are linked to each other, hence a correlation between the two is drawn. Cp. figure 5.8 on page 116.

Using the embedded sensor, the maximum temperature deviation is in the range of 0.6–2.0 °C with the highest density around 1.1°C . The derived time $\tau_{2,resurf}$ is in the range of 70–100 minutes for most of the time.

Using the infra-red sensor, the maximum temperature deviation is in the range of 0.1–1.0°C . The highest density of values using this sensor are observed in the range of 0.1–0.6°C and for $\tau_{2,resurf}$ in the range of 10–40 minutes. Cp. figure 5.8 on page 116.

The presented values are influenced by indoor conditions, as well by the overall system performance for analysed re-surfacings. Hence, an uncertainty regarding these results has to be considered. Depending on the illustration, results should rather be compared in relative than in absolute terms. This applies to the derived energy consumption throughout re-surfacings as well as for the overall re-surfacing time τ_{resurf} . Both are linked and are influenced to a high degree by the time in-between re-surfacings.

However, it can be concluded that the control concept with the infra-red sensor leads to a reduction of the deviation of ice temperature from its set point, compared to the control concept using an embedded sensor. Linked to this, the time needed to stabilize this temperature back on the set point is reduced with the infra-red sensor. On the other hand, a higher volatility in the control loop with this control concept can result in an increased stress for system components.

Figure 5.7: Comparison of ice temperature control concepts. The time needed to stabilize the ice temperature back on its set point has been reduced comparing the infra-red sensor to the embedded sensor.

Figure 5.8: Correlation between deviation of the ice temperature from the set point and time needed to stabilize the ice temperature back on the latter.
 (Marked area in the topmost plot: 10%–90% quantile. Density plot using 50 levels).

5.4.2 CO₂ rink mass flow and –pressure drop

The deduced CO₂ rink mass flow is around 0.45–0.8 kg/s for 50% of the derived data, with a median at 0.55 kg/s. The main CO₂ mass flow is in the range of around 0.45–0.75 kg/s. The median of the main CO₂ mass flow is around 0.65 kg/s. Cp. figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9: Comparison of the main CO₂ mass flow and the CO₂ rink floor mass flow. Data: *Period 1* and *Period 2*.

The correlation of this deduced CO₂ rink floor mass flow and the rink pump signal shows a linear behaviour. The number of observed values is small, hence the significance of this correlation is low. Yet, the distribution of deduced rink floor mass flow is reasonable. Cp. figure 5.10.

Figure 5.10: Deduced CO₂ rink floor mass flow as a function of the rink floor pump signal.

The difference of receiver– and rink floor tubes inlet pressure is the pressure drop over the rink floor tubes. This pressure drop is in the range of around –0.5 to 0bar, while the median is around –0.2bar. As both pressure sensors show a step–wise behaviour, the pressure drop shows a step–wise behaviour as well. Cp. figure 5.11 on the next page.

Figure 5.11: Overview over receiver-, rink floor tubes inlet pressure and pressure drop.
Data: *Period 1* and *Period 2*.

Rink floor mass flow and –pressure drop are linked to each other. The higher the rink floor mass flow, the higher the differential pressure between the inlet of the rink floor tubes and the receiver. As mentioned before, the pressure drop is around -0.2bar for 50% of the time, which is considerably small. The accuracy of the pressure sensors at the same time is rather small, as the resolution is at one decimal place for both pressure sensors. Cp. the original data correlation in figure 5.12 on the facing page.

Figure 5.12: Correlation between mass flow and pressure drop in the rink tubes.

6 Conclusions and suggestions for future works

Using the *pandas* package for Python, functionalities of the package have been combined in order to prepare- and re-sample raw data provided by the IWMAC web interface. Different re-sampling resolutions have been compared with the raw data using correlation coefficients and a sufficient resolution of 1 minute has been identified.

For the analysis of correlations between two variables, a function for the sector-wise calculation of quantiles has been designed. This allows for visualizing trends for such correlation.

The system behaviour regarding energy demand and system performance has been evaluated for two periods: *Period 1* (December 2014 to March 2015) and *Period 2* (August 2015 to December 2015). It has been shown that the heat demand of this facility is dominant compared to the cooling demand. Comparing the system performance throughout the two periods, it has been shown that this performance could have been optimized. For the major share of operating conditions, the discharge pressure could be lowered in order to enhance the system performance.

The dehumidification system, which consumed considerable amounts of electric energy throughout warm periods of the year, could be adapted to fit the available temperature level better. Thus, a considerable reduction of electric energy for warm periods could be achieved.

Depending on the lower temperature level of the hot water circuit, it has been shown for two simplified scenarios that the heat recovery potential is in the range of 50- to more than 100kW, depending on the lower temperature level and heat demands of other consumers in the circuit.

Using a regression over a certain temperature level of the geothermal storage return temperature, an increase of the latter over the first periods of around 1°C has been shown. Furthermore, a calculated median efficiency of the geothermal storage heat exchanger *HX2* of around 50% illustrates an optimization potential of this component.

Utilizing measured data, parameter variations and a function of two variables using a linear regression, a theoretical study of the system performance using an internal heat exchanger has been carried out. It has been shown that the coefficient of performance of this theoretical model can be improved using an internal heat exchanger. At the same time, a reduction of heat potential for the usage in the heat recovery system of at most 10% can be expected for the theoretical model.

The ice temperature control has been examined using an algorithm. This allowed for the analysis of two variables with significance for the ice quality: The maximum temperature deviation from the set-point and the time needed to stabilize this temperature back on its set-point. It has been illustrated that the infra-red sensor control concepts outperforms a control concept using an embedded sensor in terms of these two variables.

Using filtered data by super-heat conditions of the CO₂ mass flow in the rink tubes return, the rink mass flow has been deduced. A correlation between this mass flow and the rink pump signal

shows a reasonable connection of the two variables. This suggests that the CO₂ rink mass flow is at maximum around 1.3 kg/s for a rink pump signal of 100%.

Gimo, as a complex system, offers further optimization evaluation potential, of which some are suggested below.

Overall system control The overall system control concept can be optimized. As it has been shown, the overall system performance can be increased by stabilizing the discharge pressure better on the calculated optimum. The gas cooler control concept involving the dry cooler and the geothermal storage can be enhanced by maintaining a more stable heat rejection to the geothermal storage, thus reducing the overall volatility of the system.

Hot water circuit A further analysis of the heat potential can be carried out.

Dehumidifier The dehumidifier heat supply can be optimized by either using a dehumidification system that fits the available temperature level better, or using a heat exchanger for this system at the highest available temperature level in the system — the discharge side of the compressors.

Geothermal storage The control concept involving the geothermal storage needs further evaluation. Short-term and long-term control concepts can be developed, involving the current demand and predicted demand of heat and cold quantities. This is reasonable in order to ensure a good overall system performance, not only for a short period but instead from a broad perspective. For example, the geothermal storage temperature level can be controlled to match the application as a heat sink or heat source. As both applications are primarily needed in different seasons, a long term control concept can be reasonable. Still, the operation of the geothermal storage as heat source needs further evaluation. Furthermore, the geothermal storage heat exchanger *HX2* can be optimized to fit the available temperature levels on both sides better.

Internal heat exchanger The further analysis and integration of an internal heat exchanger could be carried out in the future.

Developed Python scripts The developed Python scripts and functions can be adapted and used for future projects.

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